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EFFECTIVENESS OF NEWS FOR DETECTION AND MANAGEMENT OF
SEPSIS IN ONCOLOGY PATIENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

This quality improvement investigation explored the effectiveness of implementing the National Early Warning Score (NEWS) as a screening tool for detecting early indicators of sepsis in medical oncology patients. The original NEWS (Smith et al., 2013) was modified to account for changes in physiologic components associated with sepsis. Seven parameters were included as separate items, and rubrics were identified for scoring each item to determine a composite score (i.e., the NEWS). A “paper protocol” was designed for nurses as part of every 4 hour monitoring; a NEWS value of ≥ 6 required an assessment by a medical team and institution of a sepsis treatment bundle.

Following a series of pilot studies that showed the NEWS to accurately predict sepsis (92% at time of screening; 42% 4 hours prior to screening), unit-wide implementation of the NEWS plus treatment bundle occurred March 1, 2015. Comparison data of patients over six months (March – August) on the same medical oncology units with an ICD of sepsis, but a year earlier (pre-NEWS, 2014), were used to calculate a proxy NEWS value. Of 3,882 paper protocol records of patients, 32 pre-NEWS and 26 post-NEWS patients had NEWS ≥ 6 and were evaluated for differences in demographic and clinical characteristics. The post-NEWS group averaged 10 years younger than the comparison group ($p \leq .01$), had fewer patients suffering from hypertension or Type II diabetes mellitus (though more had chronic obstructive

pulmonary disease), and had different cancer profiles. More pre-NEWS patients (89%) were categorized in severe sepsis compared to 69% pre implementation ($p < .073$). No differences were found in the time to treatment (0 – 60 minutes for 50% post-NEWS group vs. 47% pre-NEWS group). Five patients died in the post-NEWS group; 9 died in the pre-NEWS group. Analysis of NEWS values 4 hours before and at time of NEWS alert demonstrated no statistically significant difference, indicating missed opportunities to initiate medical team response and initiation of treatment bundle.

Findings indicate the need for additional staff and provider education to ensure adherence to all protocol components to avoid “missed” alerts. Additionally, a computerized tool or application should be built into the electronic medical record for accurate real time sepsis detection. Most importantly, the NEWS tool enhanced awareness of screening for sepsis.

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BACKGROUND

Treatment of hematologic and solid tumor malignancies with intensive cytotoxic chemotherapy can lead to neutropenia and risk for sepsis. Advances in approaches to empiric broad spectrum antimicrobial therapy and prophylaxis have resulted in improved patient outcomes. Mortality in septic patients, however, remains as high as 50% in high-risk cancer populations (Thursky & Worth, 2015). There is a recognized need for early identification of sepsis to enable timely administration of antibiotic therapy to decrease the incidence of severe sepsis, septic shock, mortality, intensive care unit (ICU) admission, and healthcare costs attributed to longer hospital stays.

According to Bone et al. (1992), the term systemic inflammatory response (SIRS) refers to a form of dysregulated inflammation and has been associated with infectious sepsis and non-infectious events such as pancreatitis, vasculitis, thromboembolism, burns and surgery. Sepsis refers to the systemic response to infection. Severe sepsis is defined as sepsis with acute organ dysfunction while “septic shock” refers to sepsis with organ dysfunction and hypotension refractory to fluid resuscitation (Levy et al., 2001). In the immune compromised host, risk factors for sepsis are increased due to tumor burden or chemo-toxic agents and the body’s ability to fight infection when there is a low neutrophil count. The 2014 guidelines from the German Society of Hematology and Medical Oncology (DGHO) endorse a set of diagnostic criteria for oncology patients which includes a multinational association for supportive care in cancer (MASCC) score of less than 21, hypophosphatemia, hypoproteinemia, pulmonary infection, hyperlactemia that differ significantly to the SIRS criteria used by the international Surviving Sepsis Campaign’s (SSC) 2012 recommendations (Thursky & Worth, 2015). Neutropenia as an

additional contributor in oncology patients, is defined as an absolute neutrophil count (ANC) of less than $500/\text{mm}^3$ or an ANC that is expected to decrease to less than 500 cells/ mm^3 within the next 48 hours. Fever is another critical component in the DGHO guidelines and is defined as a single oral temperature of greater than 38.3°C (101°F) or 38.0°C (100.4°F) for more than 1 hour (Freifeld et al., 2011). Neutropenic fever, a well-known phenomenon in the oncology population caused by chemo-toxic agents, can result in progression to sepsis and admission to the ICU if not managed adequately.

Financial Burden

Although pharmaceutical companies have manufactured more robust antibiotics to combat infection, in-hospital sepsis and septicemia remain a costly burden to the patient as well as the institution. In 2008, the percentage of patients with septicemia more than doubled to 24% from 11.6% in 2000 per 10,000 individuals (Hall, Williams, DeFrances, & Golosinskiy, 2011). A recent financial analysis of hospital expenditures by Lagu et al. (2012) reported that the total hospital costs for all patients with severe sepsis increased from \$15.4 billion in 2003 to \$24.3 billion in 2007, a 57% increase. These numbers did not separate neutropenic from general population sepsis, which is considered later in this discussion. Determinants of this increasing admission rate are thought to include an aging population with more chronic illnesses, greater use of invasive procedures, immunosuppressive drugs, chemotherapy, transplantation, and increasing microbial resistance to antibiotics (Gaijeski, Edwards, & Carr, 2013; Torio & Andrews, 2013).

For optimum management of septic patients, it is important to consider the *golden hours*—the period in which definitive recognition and treatment provide the maximum

benefit. In 2001, the Institute of Medicine proposed that physicians adopt practice interventions based on best evidence to improve patients' outcomes (Flynn-Makic, Rauen, Watson, & Poteet, 2014). The mission of the SSC was the widespread adoption of practice improvement programs grounded in EGDT with the goal of improving the diagnosis and treatment of sepsis (Levy et al., 2010). The guidelines incorporated several key tenets, including screening high-risk patients by collecting bacterial cultures prior to starting broad spectrum antibiotics, draining abscesses, and administering intravenous fluids to correct decreased blood volume and maintain glycemic control (Dellinger et al., 2008, 2013). Protocols were developed that identified treatment bundles resulting in a 16% reduction in the in-hospital absolute mortality rate associated with sepsis compared to control subjects receiving standard care (Levy et al., 2010).

An important recommendation related to the implementation of EGDT and sepsis bundles was the administration of empiric antibiotics within 1 hour of a suspected diagnosis of sepsis without waiting for culture results. Kumar et al. (2006) showed that the initiation of antibiotic therapy within the first hour following the onset of septic shock-related hypotension was associated with a 79.9% survival to hospital discharge rate. Consequently, early identification of sepsis in at-risk oncology patients, administration of a treatment bundle, and "golden hour" timing are the three factors that demand healthcare providers' attention.

Problem Statement

Failure to identify early warning signs of sepsis has dire consequences for the patient who, upon ICU admission, is already significantly behind in needed treatment and symptom management due to hematologic infection and end organ damage from

hypotension (Cuthbertson, Boroujerdi, Mckie, Aucott, & Prescott, 2007). Furthermore, delayed sepsis management can incur significant health care expenditures due to the higher level of care needed and the increased length of hospital stay. Daniels, Nutbeam, McNamara, and Galvin, 2011) advocated for the early detection and expedient management of hypotensive septic patients on medical–surgical units with intravenous fluids and empiric broad spectrum antibiotics.

The National Early Warning Score

The National Early Warning Score (NEWS) was designed to assist nurses in recognizing adults exhibiting subtle changes in physiologic parameters that typically occur within 1 hour prior to cardiopulmonary arrest. The ideal original score on NEWS to signal a medical assessment team (MAT) code is 7, but it was modified to 6 for this doctoral work, as the pilot study in October 2014 demonstrated that fewer patients were identified by a NEWS score of 7 and therefore a score of 6 was a more sensitive indicator; however, any score warrants a response, particularly if the nurse judges a patient to be clinically compromised. In 2007, the Acute Medicine Task Force of the Royal College of Physicians recommended that the physiological assessment of all patients should be standardized across UK's National Health System (NHS) by recording a minimum clinical data set and implementing NEWS in all hospitals. The NEWS has undergone substantial, positive evaluation, outperforming 33 other early warning systems (EWS) in its ability to pinpoint patients at risk of cardiac arrest, unanticipated ICU admission, and death within 24 hours (Smith, Prytherch, Meredith, Schmidt, & Featherstone, 2013). As there is a compelling need to develop and test an early intervention sepsis tool for oncology patients, this project focused on implementation and

analysis of data from a pilot study to investigate the effectiveness of a sepsis tool and treatment bundle for oncology patients that represents an adaptation of the original 2012 NEWS.

Goal

The goal of this quality improvement project was to improve the management of neutropenic septic oncology patients at a tertiary care medical center in the Western United States. Thus, the purpose of the project was to evaluate the efficacy of the NEWS tool by comparing time to treatment, adherence to the protocol, nurse compliance, and mortality rates in septic oncology patients in a period before implementation of this tool and bundle with the same length of time after implementation of the tool and the bundle.

The project aims included the following:

1. Evaluate the efficacy of the NEWS tool by comparing patient outcomes (time to treatment, nurse compliance, and sepsis related mortality) in 32 patients managed for sepsis prior to NEWS implementation (pre-NEWS group) from March 1, 2014 to August 31, 2014 and 26 patients after NEWS implementation (post-NEWS group) from March 1, 2015 to August 31, 2015, matched on age, cancer type, infections, and comorbidities
2. Evaluate the adherence to a sepsis treatment protocol from March 1, 2015 to August 31st, 2015.
3. Identify how patient level factors (clinical and demographic attributes) and nursing expertise influence adherence to the NEWS tool and patient outcomes.
4. Evaluate the 4-hour before vital sign 2015 data prior to the final NEWS data.

Supporting Framework

Cause and Effect of Delayed Recognition of Sepsis

A diagnosis of sepsis in a neutropenic patient bestows a higher rate of clinical deterioration, ICU admission, and mortality. The first step in planning this quality improvement doctoral project was to undertake a root cause analysis of the problem. This was necessary before the investigator could determine the appropriate model for improvement to work through the problem. The problem was defined as the lack of a standardized protocol for the management of SIRS or sepsis that followed the 2012 SSC guidelines at the medical center. This problem can best be illustrated utilizing a fish bone diagram shown in Figure 1.

A fishbone diagram was a useful brainstorming tool to utilize due to its simplicity of design and ability to identify the root cause for the lack of early sepsis detection (lack of clinician awareness, no evidence-based standardized protocols, complex patients with multiple chemotherapy protocols, and lack of stakeholder buy-in). The effect resulted in delayed management of sepsis patients. The developer of the fishbone diagram was Dr. Kaoru Ishikawa (1968), a Japanese quality control statistician. It is often also referred to as the Ishikawa diagram and was created to provide a systematic way of looking at effects and the causes that create or contribute to these effects. In this doctoral project, the fishbone diagram illustrates impediments to the development of an evidence-based sepsis protocol.

Improvement Indicators

Having outlined the cause and effects related to sepsis management, the next step was to identify project improvement indicators as shown in Figure 2. The national in-

Figure 1. Fishbone diagram to analyze the delayed recognition of sepsis.

hospital mortality rate for sepsis in 2009 was 16% (Elixhauser, Friedman, & Stranges, 2011). There is a paucity of data on neutropenic sepsis related mortality. Thus, the target goal for this project as a result of the NEWS screening tool was reduction of mortality by 10% to meet the 2016 goal of the sepsis committee at the medical center.

Other expected outcomes, as illustrated in Figure 2, were to administer intravenous fluids and antibiotics with the other components of the treatment bundle within 1 hour. The NEWS nurse scores and sepsis category compliance were also measured. Comparison data was provided by a retrospective record review of 2014 patient data, which met the inclusion criteria but did not utilize a screening tool or treatment bundle.

Figure 2. Project improvement indicators.

PDSA Model

The PDSA model was conceptualized by Dr. W. Edwards Deming, who was known as the founder of quality control. He was an American statistician, professor, author, lecturer, and consultant. The concept of PDSA has its roots in the scientific method, developed from the work of Francis Bacon (*Novum Organum*, 1620). The scientific method includes four steps: (a) hypothesis, (b) experiment, (c) evaluation, and (d) check. A fundamental principle of the scientific method and PDSA is iteration and is illustrated in Figure 3. Once a hypothesis is confirmed (or negated), executing the cycle again will further extend knowledge on the subject. Repeating the PDSA cycle can bring one closer to the goal, elusive as it may be, of a perfect project outcome. The PDSA is an appropriate model for this quality improvement project because this is an iterative process involving multiple phases; further, it addresses the many stages within the context of the people, places, and obstacles that may be encountered.

Figure 3. PDCA concept model illustrating the various phases of project development.

Screening for Sepsis and Performance Improvement Indicators

The content from the International Guidelines for management of severe sepsis and septic shock (Dellinger et al., 2013) was used as a blueprint for this quality improvement project. The recommendations from the 2014 German Society of Hematology and Medical Oncology (DGHO) were also considered and include other prognostic indicators. However, they do not consider screening for early sepsis. The recommendations were adapted to cancer patients in a medical oncology unit. The surviving sepsis guidelines recommend screening to increase the early identification of sepsis and allow implementation of early sepsis therapy. The early identification of sepsis and implementation of early evidence-based therapies have been documented to improve outcomes and decrease sepsis-related mortality (Levy et al., 2010).

Reducing the time to diagnose severe sepsis is thought to be a critical component of reducing mortality from sepsis-related multiple organ dysfunction (Jones & Shapiro,

2010). Lack of early recognition is a major obstacle to sepsis bundle initiation. Sepsis screening tools have been developed to monitor ICU patients (Moore et al., 2009), and their implementation has been associated with decreased sepsis-related mortality (Levy et al., 2010).

The surviving sepsis guidelines as delineated in a paper by Dellinger et al. (2004, 2008, 2013), in partnership with the Institute for Healthcare Improvement, targeted the implementation of a core set (i.e., bundle) of recommendations in hospital environments where change in behavior and clinical impact were measured. The SSC guidelines and bundles can be used as the basis of a sepsis performance improvement program and are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Surviving Sepsis Guidelines (Dellinger et al., 2004, 2008, 2012)

	Clinical symptoms	1st Line action	2nd Line action	2nd Line continued	Goal
1- hour completion (medical floor)	SBP < 90 or MAP < 70 mm Hg or SBP < 40 mm Hg below normal	Isotonic crystalloids or albumin. Administer 20 ml/kg IV bolus over 5-10 minutes	Antibiotics within one hour. Combination therapy for neutropenic septic patients	Cultures prior to antimicrobial therapy.	Reverse hypotension, increasing urine output and restore level of consciousness
3-hour completion (medical floor)		Lactic acid, blood cultures, administer broad spectrum antibiotics	Administer broad spectrum antibiotics	Administer 30ml/kg IV fluid for hypotension or lactate 4 mmol/L	Reverse hypotension, increasing urine output and restore level of consciousness
6-hour completion (ICU)	MAP < 70 mm Hg	Vasopressors for hypotension refractory to IV fluids to keep map > or = 65 mm Hg			Reverse hypotension, increasing urine output and restore level of consciousness

Prior to the implementation of this doctoral project, the medical center had embarked on a plan to improve the identification and management of sepsis in oncology patients using a multi-phase approach. This cyclical process involved increased complexity at each phase, and encompassed a paper nurse-driven protocol, the NEWS tool with the treatment bundle and data collection. A sepsis committee met bi-weekly to review the planning phases and to identify project leaders and nurse champions. Buy-in was secured from the chief nursing officer, the medical director for pulmonary critical care, and hematology/oncology services.

PDSA Project Cycle

Phase 1

From October 1, 2014 to November 31, 2014, a sepsis committee was formed and staff met biweekly. Members included medical director, nurse practitioners (NPs), registered nurses (RNs) and certified nurse anesthetists (CNAs) from the medical oncology units. The current evidence-based literature was reviewed, and the NEWS tool was chosen to screen for early sepsis.

Phase 2

From November 31, 2014 until December 31, 2014, the NEWS tool was piloted on two medical oncology units at the medical center. Of the 34 patients selected for this initial screening using NEWS, 12 patients had a positive sepsis screening (NEWS score of 7).

Phase 3

From January 1, 2015 until March 1, 2015, a treatment bundle was added to the NEWS and utilized in the pilot project on two medical units and 4th floor ICU at the

medical center. From March 1, 2015 to August 31, 2015, the screening tool and protocol were implemented on two oncology units and the ICU.

Phase 4

A retrospective data analysis of septic cancer patients was evaluated with the NEWS and received treatment based on their NEWS scores or clinical judgment. The project development is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2

Pilot Study of NEWS and the Sepsis Treatment Bundle

	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3	Cycle 4
PDSA	Oct 1 to Nov 31 2014	Dec 1 to Dec 31 2014	Jan 1 to August 31,2015	Sept 1 to Present 2015-2016
PLAN	Conceptualized and developed a nurse-driven protocol.	Implemented NEWS as a pilot study on medical units.	Developed and utilized the NEWS + txt bundle for sepsis detection.	Retrospective analysis of five months of data from Phase 4.
DO	Distributed journal articles on EWS and NEWS.	17 RNs collected NEWS data on 34 oncology pts.	Data collected once per shift by the charge RN. Data entered into Excel.	Analyzed de-identified data collected in Excel.
STUDY	RN staff utilized online learning modules to add NEWS.	Analyzed data on NEWS, sens, spec, and time to txt bundle.	Data: time to txt variable, # of ICU admissions, MAT codes, and mortalities.	Answer research question; NEWS + time to txt. Demographics and sepsis types
ACT	NEWS scoring improved with practice. More training needed.	Modified NEWS to detect sepsis in medical oncology pts.	There were more frequent MAT calls. Analyze data monthly.	TBD: Successful outcome and interventions in sepsis mgmt.

Note: RN(s) = registered nurse(s), NEWS = National Early Warning System, Oct = October, Nov = November, Dec = December, pts = patients, txt = treatment, sens = sensitivity, spec = specificity, MAT = medical assessment team, # = number, TBD = to be determined, mgmt. = management.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The review of literature focuses on the incidence of sepsis and associated health care costs. It includes a discussion on immunodeficiency as a prognostic indicator of mortality, timely antibiotic administration, screening systems, and risk factors for sepsis.

Incidence and Expenditures

The incidence of sepsis has more than doubled from 2000 to 2008 in the United States. A health brief presented by Hall et al. (2011) for the Department of Health and Human Services found that the rate of sepsis or septicemia has more than doubled, from 11.6 to 24.0 per 10,000 patients (326,000 cases in 2000 to 727,000 cases in 2008). With the inclusion of a secondary diagnosis of septicemia or sepsis, the rates increased to 37.7 per 10,000 patients, or over 1.1 million cases. Nationally, sepsis is the single most expensive condition treated in hospitals; it is responsible for only 2.8% of all hospitalizations but 5.3% of all hospital costs, amounting to \$20.3 billion dollars annually (Gaieski et al., 2013).

Immunodeficiency and Mortality

A systematic review by Thursky and Worth (2015) considered studies that identified risks for mortality in neutropenic patients. Neutropenic fever in patients receiving cytotoxic chemotherapy varies with underlying malignancy, 5% to 10% in solid tumors to 100% in high risk bone marrow transplantation. Gram negative bacteria confer the highest rate of mortality in febrile neutropenic patients. Early detection of sepsis and valid tools for clinical assessment are beneficial for screening. Overall improved recognition of neutropenic sepsis facilitate administration of antimicrobial therapy and

reduce mortality. Tolsma et al. (2014) attempted to evaluate the role of immunosuppression as an indicator for survival. They conducted an observational study that used data from 11 French ICUs; the data were prospectively entered from January 1997 to August 2011. All patients entered into the database had a sepsis diagnosis. The immunocompromised patients were defined according to seven immunodeficiency profiles: (a) acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), (b) organ transplant, (c) solid organ tumor without neutropenia, (d) hematologic malignancy without neutropenia, (e) all-cause neutropenia, (f) inflammatory and/or immune disorder, and (g) primary or congenital immunodeficiency. Patients with a solid tumor or with hematologic malignancy were classified in the neutropenic group. The results indicated that immunodeficiency was a poor independent prognosis factor for survival, while some causes are associated with a greater risk of death at day 28, such as AIDS, any malignant disease without neutropenia, or neutropenia regardless of its cause. This study illustrated the importance of including this profile in studies regarding sepsis outcomes which were found to be higher among immune compromised patients.

Time to Treatment: Antibiotics

A landmark study by Rivers et al. (2001) determined the benefits of EGDT in terms of mortality outcome in the treatment of severe sepsis and septic shock. In addition, EGDT provided at the earliest possible stages has significant short- and long-term benefits due to the recognition of those patients with high risk for cardiovascular collapse. Treatment involves the use of intravenous fluids, blood transfusions, and inotropic support. In the EGDT group, intravenous fluid boluses appeared to have a

statistically significant impact. The benefits of EGDT resulted in less mortality due to cardiac arrest.

Relatively few studies have rigorously examined the effect of delays in antimicrobial therapy in the oncology population. The National Chemotherapy Advisory Group identified the importance of administering intravenous antibiotics within 60 minutes of a neutropenic fever. Higgins and Hill (2012) performed a retrospective audit of the South West London Cancer Network neutropenic sepsis clinical pathway over a 4-month period (September 2010 to February 2011) to assess network-wide adherence to the clinical pathway. The data collection comprised a case note analysis, a questionnaire for visits to specific departments, and a patient questionnaire. Results showed that 23% of patients received antibiotics within 1 hour, while the majority, 52%, received antibiotic therapy in more than 2 but fewer than 8 hours. Of the patient experience questionnaires, 33% were returned. Overall, the results were not on target with the projected 1-hour timeline and highlighted issues with accessing specific antibiotics.

A larger, widely cited retrospective study by Kumar et al. (2006) conducted between July 1989 and June 2004 in 14 ICUs (in Canada and the United States) involved 2,731 patients. Documented infections were present in 77.9% of the cases. The remaining 22.1% of the cases represented suspected infections without a plausible pathogen. The overall mortality rate was 56.2%. Of the 2,731 patients with septic shock, 19 did not receive effective antimicrobials before death, and 558 were on antimicrobial therapy that was matched to a defined pathogen or undefined pathogen. For the remaining 2,154 patients who received effective antimicrobials only after the onset of hypotension, the mortality rate was 58.0%. Given its scale, this study provides strong

evidence that a delay in the initiation of effective antimicrobial therapy is a therapeutic variable associated with septic shock mortality. Furthermore, the administration of antibiotics within 1 hour following the onset of septic shock-related hypotension was associated with a 79.9% survival to discharge rate. Each additional hour without effective antimicrobial treatment in the first 6 hours after hypotension onset was associated with a 7.6% increase in mortality.

In a retrospective case study in a tertiary care medical center, Lynn, Chen, Weng, and Chiu (2013) identified latency of the first antibiotics, pneumonia, and a platelet count $< 50,000/\text{mm}^3$ as independent risk factors associated with serious complications in neutropenic patients. The results confirmed previous studies' findings that delay to time of antibiotic administration were associated with increased severity of illness in neutropenic patients. The findings, however, have limited applicability, as this was a small-scale study with 78 patients confined to one tertiary care center.

Screening Systems and Standardized Procedures

Many severely ill patients have both acute and chronic illnesses. The rationale for using scoring systems, therefore, is to ensure that the increased complexity of disease in patients currently being treated is consistently represented in evaluations and descriptions; it is a means to document where along the continuum the patient resides (Bone et al., 1992).

Moore et al. (2009) used a cloud-based clinical application screening tool on systemic inflammatory response system (SIRS) indicators, but they used a range of values for temperature (T), heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR), and white cell count adapted from a severity of illness scoring system. Numerical values assigned to each

category reflected the level of deviance from the norm and were combined to determine a SIRS score.

Duckitt et al. (2007) used a validated physiologic scoring tool to screen patients in the emergency room setting admitted to medical wards. The physiological tool had a sensitivity of 0.71 and a specificity of 0.77. This study is significant because it was the first to predict patient mortality in medical wards admitted from emergency rooms utilizing a large sample size and a simple scoring system.

A quality improvement project in the form of a descriptive study by Fitzpatrick, Mckenna, Rooney, Beckett, and Pringle (2014) utilized a physiological scoring system to study the ability of ambulance clinicians to competently predict clinical deterioration at the time of pickup and then assessed emergency room personnel's perceptions. The responses to a 5-point Likert scale were favorable regarding ambulance clinicians' ability to make initial assessments and initiate interventions prior to admission to the emergency room. Due to the low number of cases used in the study, the results are not generalizable; however, the study does open up the opportunity for future studies on the use of the tool in ambulatory care settings.

Cuthbertson et al. (2007) tested components of early warning screening tools to determine their ability to identify clinical deterioration. The data were collected from patients in a high dependency unit (HDU) in England and consisted of the following physiologic variables: heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), temp (T), oxygen saturation (SpO₂), urine volume, and level of consciousness (LOC). Discrete early warning scoring system scores were also collected. The results showed that HR, RR, SBP, T, and SpO₂ had an Area Under a Receiver Operating Curve

(AUROC) of 0.90 (95% confidence interval [CI]). Within the discriminant analysis, HR and RR had the highest values. Results indicated that the discrete scores on the tests had good predictive accuracy for identifying the deteriorating patient and that the individual physiologic variables had moderate predictive accuracy. Lopez-Bushnell, Demaray, and Jaco (2014) piloted a screening tool to detect early sepsis on two medical–surgical units. In total, 225 patients screened positive for sepsis over a 4-year period. Of particular significance in terms of outcomes were serum lactate values, blood cultures prior to antibiotic initiation, and time-oriented treatments. The overall goal was to institute a standardized order set to reduce the number of mortalities due to sepsis, which declined by 30% after implementation of the tool.

In the Medical Emergency Response and Intervention, Buist et al. (2002) tested the effects of an emergency response team (ERT). The ERT consisted of two doctors and one senior nurse who attended to the clinically unstable patients. By virtue of having this response team, the incidence of cardiac arrest was 3.77 per 1000 hospital admissions (73 cases pre intervention) and 2.05 per 1000 hospital interventions (47 cases post intervention), and mortality was 77% and 55%, respectively. Mortality was reduced by 20% by the presence of an emergency response team.

After NEWS was implemented in 2012 in the UK, on the recommendation of the Royal College of Physicians as a valid tool for assessing clinical deterioration, a study to validate this assertion was conducted by Smith et al. (2013). The study included entering vital signs into a Vital Pac software program between May 2006 and June 2008. The outcomes measured were unanticipated ICU admission, cardiac death, and other causes of mortality that were recorded within a 24-hour period. The values for the AUROC—a

common statistical test to determine a tool's ability to discriminate an outcome measure—that were calculated for NEWS related to cardiac arrest, unanticipated ICU admission, death, and any other outcomes, all within 24 hours. The NEWS held up against outcomes of vital importance to patients and staff, demonstrating a good ability to identify patients at risk of cardiac arrest, unanticipated ICU admission, or death within 24 hours.

Yu et al. (2014) tested multiple scoring systems and found that eight of nine systems predicted clinical deterioration 12 hours prior to clinical compromise and had good AUROC of (0.70). Additionally, the emergency room and ICU scoring systems can be used successfully on non-ICU patients. NEWS had an AUC 0.75 and will detect clinical deterioration on medical patients.

Risk Factors

Sepsis is a life-threatening medical condition characterized by an overwhelming systemic inflammatory response to infection. Although sepsis can occur independently of risk factors, studies have documented changing demographics, potent and broader-spectrum antibiotics, immunosuppressive agents, and invasive technology used in the treatment of inflammatory, infectious, and neoplastic diseases as some of the major factors causing sepsis (Bone et al., 1992)

Several risk factors are involved in clinical deterioration with septic neutropenic patients and include age over 65 years, poor performance response, previous episodes of febrile neutropenia, cytopenias, congestive heart failure (CHF), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and chronic kidney disease (CKD). Tolsma et al. (2014) showed that immunodeficiency such as AIDS and/or any malignant disease without

neutropenia was an independent poor prognostic indicator for survival and associated with greater risk of death at D28, and that neutropenia regardless of its cause was associated with D28 mortality. Mokart et al. (2014) found that antimicrobial therapy can decrease the length of ICU stays and allows effective de-escalation of empiric antibiotics, while obtaining two blood cultures before empiric antibiotics helped match the antimicrobial with the target organism, improving patient outcomes. Neutropenic patients require immediate attention regarding antibiotics and blood cultures, and antibiotic stewardship is associated with decreased mortality in this population group.

Standardized Procedures

Standardized procedures can lead to improved healthcare outcomes for patients with sepsis. The management of critically ill patients varies considerably during each nursing assignment and depends entirely on the skills, judgment, and experience of the staff members on duty (Buist et al., 2002). This inconsistency leads to a poorly standardized approach to patient care. To address this issue in a study of 4,329 ICU adult patients between 2004 and 2010, Miller et al. (2013) found that compliance with early resuscitation elements completed within the first 3 hours after emergency room (ED) admission predicted less need for inotropes, blood transfusions, ventilation, and glucocorticoids. Compliance with the total bundle decreased mortality rate by 55% over the study period from 21.9% at baseline in 2004 to 9.7% in 2010.

Additionally, standardized nursing assessment tools have emerged and are being investigated as to their effectiveness in assisting nurses to identify patients exhibiting early signs of clinical deterioration and thus to reduce failure to rescue events. These tools or warning systems link physiologic parameters with specific nursing actions.

Cuthbertson et al. (2007) found that a graduated intervention physiologic scoring system can predict clinical deterioration, as using a smaller number of variables had superior predictive accuracy. For example, the NEWS is one example of a screening tool developed to improve the early identification and rescue of patients who are clinically deteriorating on units outside the ICU by employing a consistent assessment system to be used by all nurses regardless of experience.

Smith et al. (2013) elaborated on the scoring process, assigning a criteria-based numerical value to a patient's behavioral, cardiac, and respiratory status. Information is obtained through the routine course of nursing assessments using the NEWS grid and normal vital sign parameters as determined by each individual institution. Moore et al. (2009) developed an evidence-based patient specific protocol for the management of patients in the SICU and utilized a cloud based application.

Neutropenic Sepsis

In a review of literature, Thursky and Worth (2015) summarized factors associated with reduced mortality in patients with neutropenic fever, emphasizing elements of clinical care that can be incorporated for inclusion in quality improvement programs. In all, 88 studies were reviewed, and the results showed of primary importance was multidisciplinary quality improvement strategies with clinical benefits to neutropenic fever populations, including antimicrobial stewardship programs and clinical pathways for the detection and management of sepsis. Time to first dose is an important process measure that reflects recognition of sepsis and early resuscitation.

Summary

This concise literature review has attempted to lay the foundation for the structural components of this doctoral project, which has its origins in the application of the NEWS tool to the implementation of the treatment bundle as part of a nurse driven standardized protocol. Considering studies that acknowledged the timely administration of antibiotics to address sepsis before the patient deteriorates into septic shock, incurring more ICU days, as well as increasing the risk of mortality was vital to this doctoral project. Adhering to the EDBG, protocols were subsequently developed that identified treatment bundles that resulted in a 16% reduction in the absolute mortality rate associated with sepsis; this is compared to control subjects receiving standard care (Levy et al., 2010). Furthermore, NEWS has been validated in favor of failure to rescue situations in acutely ill patients. It is the expectation of this investigator that NEWS and treatment bundle implementation will lead to an earlier detection of sepsis and a reduction in mortality. The evidence-based guidelines (EBG) have been applied to manage sepsis for over 10 years Dellinger et al. (2004, 2008, 2013), yet rates of sepsis-related mortality remain unacceptably high (Gaieski et al., 2013). For septic oncology patients, the guidelines have been adhered to with the inclusion of neutropenia as an additional risk factor for sepsis, using the recommendations from the German Society of Hematology and Medical Oncology (Penack et al., 2014). A recurrent construct related to sepsis management in this doctoral inquiry is the prompt recognition of sepsis, supported by effective screening strategies and the initiation of treatment bundles.

Although the purpose, design, and sample type for the studies presented in this concise literature review varied, each study offered useful information regarding early

sepsis detection to reduce organ damage and mortality. A table of evidence (Appendix C) provides a detailed list of the key research articles discussed. Overall, the literature yielded a lack of evidence-based research regarding the effect of screening for sepsis on medical oncology units, as most research has been focused on severe sepsis and septic shock patients in an ICU setting as documented in the SSC 2012. This doctoral study utilized the recommendations from the SSC 2012 and incorporated the key elements into the NEWS tool treatment bundle for evaluation of potentially septic oncology patients.

METHODS

This section provides the information concerning the study design, how it was conducted, research questions, and the study's operational definitions. The project was guided by the following question: "Does the implementation of a modified NEWS and bundle decrease the time to treatment, adherence to the bundle, and sepsis-related mortalities in an adult medical oncology population?" The operational definitions of terms used in this project are included for review.

Design

A retrospective design was used to evaluate the effectiveness of NEWS in identifying and managing sepsis patients in a neutropenic oncology population. Pre-intervention and post-intervention data were collected

Sample

Inclusion criteria for subjects were the following: (a) neutropenic cancer patients at various stages of cancer treatment, (b) aged 18 years and older, and (c) those treated with or without chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and targeted therapy. Exclusion criteria included the following: (a) patients for whom interventions in the protocol are clinically contraindicated (e.g., those with multiple allergies to antibiotics), (b) patients with advanced directives in place at the time of care that precluded any protocol interventions, and (c) those for whom the patient or surrogate decision-maker declined treatment via a "do not resuscitate directive".

Sampling Plan

The sample was comprised of all patients who were monitored via NEWS (post-NEWS group) during March 1, 2015 to August 31, 2015 and met the selection criteria. A

comparison patient sample (pre-NEWS group) matched on demographics and comorbidities did not receive the NEWS from March 1, 2014 to August 31, 2014.

Setting

The setting for this doctoral project was a cancer center in Southern California with a 60-bed inpatient and outpatient facility. The study involved the 3rd and 4th-floor medical oncology units and the 4th-floor ICU.

Instrument

The NEWS was modified to collect key data for septic oncology patients. The original NEWS, as described by Smith et al. (2013), was adopted in 2012 as an instrument to screen for early signs of clinical deterioration in adult patients hospitalized in units outside of ICU environments in the National Health Trust system in the UK. This tool was developed from the early warning system (EWS) work that aimed to reduce failure to rescue situations and that first came into practice in 2007. NEWS is a standardized nursing assessment tool that links physiologic parameters with specific nursing actions; however, it had not been tested on a neutropenic oncology population up to this point. The scores in NEWS as originally published range from 0 to 7 to identify those patients with deteriorating clinical status, with a higher score indicating a worsening clinical condition. NEWS data demonstrated an AUROC greater than 0.70 (Smith et al., 2013; Table 3). For this project, the sepsis team decided to investigate whether a score of 6 could be used as an early warning indicator of sepsis.

The sepsis committee at the project setting modified the original NEWS tool and used a scale for scoring sepsis risk composed of various physiologic thresholds and identifies graduated interventions as shown in Table 4. The thresholds used for the

modified NEWS are as follows: a NEWS score between 0 and 2 is labeled as SIRS, The primary outcome measure selected to determine the effectiveness of the NEWS tool was time to treatment. The time to treatment as previously defined depends on the time when the suspicion of sepsis became apparent and the sepsis bundle of interventions was

Table 3

The NEWS Tool Utilized in the Quality Improvement Project

NEWS	3	2	1	0	1	2	3
T (°C)	< 35		35 - 36	36.1 - 38	38.1 - 39	> 39	
P (bpm)	< 41		41 - 50	51 - 90	91 - 110	111 - 130	> 130
R (rpm)	< 9		9 - 11	12 - 20		21 - 24	> 24
SBP(mmHg)	< 90	90 - 100	101 - 110	111 - 220			> 220
S _O ₂ (%)	< 92	92 - 93	94 - 95	> 96			
O ₂		YES		NO			
LOC				ALERT			ALOC

Note. T = temperature, °C = degrees centigrade, P = pulse, bpm = beats per minute, R = respirations, rpm = respirations per minute, SBP = systolic blood pressure, mmHg = millimeters mercury, S_O₂ = oxygen saturation, % = percentage, O₂ = oxygen, LOC = level of consciousness, ALOC = altered level of consciousness.

Table 4

Modified NEWS and Scoring System for Presumed Septic Oncology Patients

NEWS Score	Frequency of Monitoring	Clinical Response
0-2 (SIRS; coded category 1)	Assess q every four hours	NEWS screen q shift
3-5 (Sepsis; coded category 2)	Assess q every two hours	Assess q every two hours
6 ≥ (Severe Sepsis; coded category 3)	Assess q every 15 minutes	MAT and activate txt bundle
6 ≥ + SBP < 90 (Septic Shock; coded category 4)	Continuous vital sign monitoring	IV fluids and ICU Transfer

Note. SIRS = systemic inflammatory response, 6 > = six greater than or equal to, q = every, NEWS = National Early Warning Screening, IV = intravenous, ICU = intensive care unit, MAT = medical assessment team, txt = treatment.

initiated. According to protocol and neutropenic sepsis guidelines (Penack et al., 2014), the treatment bundle must be initiated within less than 1 hour. If all bundle treatment interventions are met within the 1-hour protocol timeline, then the treatment was coded as “met,” while if even one condition was not completed, the protocol is coded as “not met.” The nurses followed a paper protocol sepsis guideline form (see Appendix A for reference only), and the approach to data collection consisted of obtaining all the NEWS paper protocol scores for the period of March 1, 2015 to August 31, 2015. Actual physiological data were recorded and then given a score based on their NEWS rating to determine scoring frequency and allow determination of sepsis category. The investigator crosschecked all NEWS score entries, and a second investigator reviewed the data on five NEWS score entries to ensure inter-rater reliability. NEWS with a score of ≥ 6 were the criteria to activate the MAT and treatment bundle.

The NEWS with the physiological measure sets (T, P, RR, SBP, O₂, O₂ Sat, LOC) corresponding to NEWS scores were recorded according to the time on the paper protocol sepsis guide, including a set 4 hours prior if data were available. The prior 4-hour recording of vital signs was done to ascertain if a sepsis trigger could have been picked up at an earlier time, which would suggest that the earlier sepsis warnings might have been missed. All paper data were transcribed to a collection study spreadsheet. (see Excel collection tool in Appendix A). The other dependent variables (as previously denoted) that correlate with a patient NEWS score of ≥ 6 were documented through chart review by this project investigator and recorded on the electronic collection spread sheet.

Protection of Human Rights

Approval for the study was obtained from the facility's quality improvement council. The project was also reviewed and approved by the California State University Long Beach (CSULB) IRB to ensure the protection of human subjects related to the use of confidential medical information.

Operational Definitions

The following terms were operationally defined for use in the study:

Acute physiology and chronic health evaluation (APACHE II): A tool to measure the severity of disease for adult patients admitted to ICUs. The point score is calculated from a patient's age and 12 physiological measures (O₂ Sat, T, mean arterial blood pressure [MAP], P, RR, serum sodium, serum potassium, serum creatinine, serum hematocrit, serum white blood cell count, and Glasgow Coma Scale). It is checked once when a patient is admitted to the ICU (Knaus, Draper, Wagner, & Zimmerman, 1985).

Calculated NEWS score: This is a computer program generated NEWS score. The components of the NEWS tool were entered into a database termed "quik base intuit" recognized to be the most accurate NEWS score. For the purpose of this project, this number was used as the NEWS score.

Comorbidity: The presence of one or more additional disorders (or diseases) co-occurring with a primary disease or the effect of such additional disorders or diseases. The following comorbid diseases were included in the data analysis: COPD, congestive heart failure (CHF), diabetes mellitus type two (DM2), end stage renal disease (ESRD), hypertension (HTN), malignant neoplasm, leukemia, and bone marrow transplant.

Dependent variables: Time to treatment, 4-hours before data, NEWS RN scores compliance, mortality rates due to sepsis.

ICD 9 Codes: The International Classification of Diseases, Clinical Modification (ICD-9-CM) is used in assigning codes to diagnoses associated with inpatient, outpatient, and physician office utilization in the United States. The following primary or secondary ICD-9 codes were utilized for this project: 038.9 (unspecified septicemia), 995.91 (sepsis), 9955.91 (severe sepsis), and 785.52 (septic shock). These codes were used to determine sepsis categories for 2014 patients in the facility. The codes were used as a surrogate measure for NEWS scores.

ICU transfers: The patients who had a NEWS score of ≥ 6 and were refractory to intravenous fluids with an SBP of < 90 who were admitted to the ICU due to severe sepsis or septic shock unless otherwise diagnosed.

Independent variable: The efficacy of NEWS to manage early sepsis.

MASCC score: Febrile neutropenia can be a risk factor for infection and is seen in patients with leukemia post chemotherapy treatments. The multinational association for supportive care in cancer (MASCC) score can be used to identify low-risk patients for serious complications, including ICU admissions and death. This scoring system was utilized as an initial assessment for all the patients in the doctoral project to determine a baseline risk as a result of febrile neutropenia (Klatersky & Paesmans, 2013). Other associated infections: bacteremia, pneumonia, line infection

Medical assessment team (MAT): The emergency response team, which including the pulmonary critical care nurse practitioner and hematology resident (at night) and the

pulmonary critical care attending (during the day). The team was to be activated for a NEWS score of ≥ 6 or by the clinical judgment of the nurse.

Mortality: Patients who died due to complications related to sepsis in the medical units or in the ICU.

Neutropenia: A neutrophil count below 500 cells/mm³ or a leukocyte count below 1,000 cells/mm³ (Mokart et al., 2014).

NEWS: A set of physiological measures that are synonymous with vital signs. It measures T in degrees centigrade (°C), P in beats per minute, RR in number of breaths per minute, SBP in mm Hg, O₂sat in percentage of oxygen, absence or presence of O₂, and LOC as awake or alert (Smith et al., 2013). A 3-point number scale is utilized to indicate increasing severity of illness from 0 being within the normal limits to 3 which is the most critical detection of illness.

Paper protocol sepsis guideline form: A nurse-driven protocol that consists of a series of interventions based on EGDT. The first step is to record a set of physiological measures, T, pulse (P), RR, SBP, SO₂, Oxygen (O₂), and LOC, and then sum the NEWS scores on the paper protocol sheet provided to each shift. The second step involves implementing the treatment bundle if the NEWS score is ≥ 6 . The last step is to reassess for further clinical deterioration, and if so, then transfer the patient to the ICU.

Post-NEWS group: Synonymous with the treatment group (the group of adult medical oncology patients at the Los Angeles Cancer Center exposed to NEWS in a pilot study from March 2015 through August 2015); the patients were studied via retrospective chart review.

Pre-NEWS group: This is synonymous with the non-treatment group (the cohort of adult medical oncology patients at the Los Angeles Cancer Center who were not exposed to NEWS); they were studied via retrospective chart review from March 2014 through August 2014. The researcher went into the database and retrieved physiological measures being studied that corresponded to the timeframe when an ICD-9 sepsis code was identified in their medical records. Because this was retrospective review, it was postulated that these patients were evaluated using the usual and customary physiological measures for clinical deterioration according to the SSC. The outcomes measures were the same for both pre-NEWS and post-NEWS and were determined via chart audit by the investigator.

Protocol compliance: The nurses NEWS paper score and agreement with the calculated medical record score.

Sepsis: This is the presence of two or more indicators of SIRS plus a known or suspected source of infection. SIRS criteria include the following: (a) a T greater than 38°C or less than 36°C, (b) a P greater than 90 beats per minute, (c) an RR greater than 20 breaths per minute, and (d) an SBP less than 90. The criteria for organ dysfunction is an SBP of less than 90 mm Hg, an SBP decrease of more than 40 mm Hg from the baseline, or an O₂ sat of less than 90% (Bone et al., 1992).

Sepsis categories: At the initiation of the study and prior to data collection, the team had identified categories of sepsis based on projected NEWS scores. Systemic inflammatory response (SIRS): an inflammatory process independent of its cause (coded by a NEWS score of 2). When SIRS is the result of confirmed infection, it is termed sepsis (coded by a NEWS score of 3 to 5). Severe sepsis is defined as sepsis-induced

organ dysfunction or tissue perfusion (coded by a NEWS score of ≥ 6) and is classified as category 3, whereas septic shock is defined as hypotension refractory to intravenous fluids coded by a NEWS score of ≥ 6 and ICU admission and is classified as category 4.

Sepsis categories redefined: After data collection, the NEWS scores for the sepsis categories had to be redefined (see #4). NEWS of 6 was coded sepsis; NEWS $6 \geq$ but < 10 was severe sepsis; NEWS ≥ 10 was coded septic shock.

Septic patient: A patient with a positive infection and two or more signs of clinical instability on NEWS.

Time to treatment: A series of nurse-driven interventions activated once the NEWS score is ≥ 6 . Interventions must be implemented within an hour and consist of the following: intravenous fluid bolus of 500 ml, repeated once if the SBP is less than 90; empiric antibiotics or change antibiotics if the microbiology results are positive; lactic acid; CBC, complete metabolic panel (CMP); protime (PT); international normalized ratio (INR); magnesium; phosphorus; blood cultures (BCs); and two sets of vital signs (peripheral and central) taken every 15 minutes (q 15 mins).

Data Collection Procedure

After permission was granted from Los Angeles Cancer Center and CSULB IRB to conduct the study, the investigator requested information from the medical records of the cohort of medical oncology patients from March 1, 2015 through August 31, 2015 (post-NEWS group) and March 1, 2014 through August 31, 2014 (pre-NEWS group), the comparison group. Data for the pre and post NEWS groups included demographics and comorbidities, with the addition of the paper protocol forms for the post-NEWS group.

Septic neutropenic patients were identified by a search in the medical records by this investigator.

Data were entered into an Excel file for the pre-and post-NEWS groups in a de-identified format according to the rules and standards of the IRB and HIPAA. The method used to de-identify information was to randomly assign each patient record, a number that did not correspond to the medical record number. For the pre-NEWS group, a printout of the electronic patient files according to a sepsis ICD-9 code were requested from the data collection office and provided in a de-identified format with a number assigned to each patient record. This de-identified number was entered into the Excel file. No identifying information (such as social security number or birthdate) was entered. All electronic patient data were password protected and stored in the principle investigator's computer; NEWS paper protocol forms were kept in a locked filing cabinet in the nurse practitioner's (NP) office with access granted to the investigator and lead sepsis RN.

After August 31, 2015, the NEWS paper protocols were collected by the principle investigator, and the data entered into an Excel file. Data included NEWS scores, times for and components of the treatment bundle, and vital signs 4 hours prior to the MAT.

The investigator reviewed the electronic medical records of the comparison group of patients to abstract the specified data needed for the study. Data recorded on the NEWS paper protocols were entered into the Excel file every 2 days starting in September of 2015 and included demographics, ICU admissions, mortality, types of cancer, and comorbidities. The same data were collected on both groups and entered into the Excel file.

A MASCC score was entered into the Excel file for all neutropenic patients. An APACHE II score was entered into the Excel file for patients admitted to the ICU.

A reliability test was conducted to ensure the data were correctly recorded by requesting an NP colleague who is familiar with the project to check five paper sepsis protocols per month and verify the NEWS scores on a random selection of NEWS protocols for both the pre-NEWS and post-NEWS groups. There was 100% concurrence.

NEWS paper protocol forms were returned to the nurse champions at the conclusion of the data collection time period.

Data Analysis

A statistician assisted with coding of variables and ran the analysis to assist with the research question. Descriptive statistics were used to quantify the numbers, means, and percentages for T, RR, SBP, and P. ANOVA was used to examine the relationship between variable variations, and an ANCOVA was used to analyze covariate effect.

RESULTS

Pilot Project

Initial piloting of the project tool and data analysis were conducted from Phase 1 through Phase 3, respectively (October 2014 to March 2015). Thirty-four patients were screened; 12 had NEWS scores of ≥ 6 and were included in the final analysis. Blood cultures in 11 (92%) of the 12 patients were positive for sepsis. The analysis indicated that NEWS correctly identified those needing further intervention. In addition, 5 (42%) of the 11 patients demonstrated increasing NEWS scores (3 to 5) 4 hours prior to the MAT alert. These patients eventually became septic, and 7 (58%) required ICU transfer. In terms of interventions, 4 (36%) patients were identified by NEWS and had an uncomplicated course of treatment, but they required fluid boluses in addition to antibiotics. This cohort remained on the medical unit under close observation. Five (46%) patients did not respond to the fluid boluses and required ICU transfer. In terms of intervention time, 3 (43%) patients received medical interventions within 4 hours but not within the 1-hour target. There were no fatalities in this group of 3; however, 4 (57%) of the 11 patients received interventions and/or ICU transfer more than 6 hours from the initial NEWS score, and 2 (50%) patients died. Based on the data, the clinical investigators were comfortable with the results of the NEWS analysis and decided to embark on the current project.

During phase 4 (March 1, 2015 to August 31, 2015), the NEWS and treatment bundle were implemented. All data from this pilot study such as time to treatment, ICU transfers and mortality were reported and incorporated into this doctoral project. Co-variables including demographics and comorbidities, such as chronic obstructive

pulmonary disease, hypertension, congestive heart failure, diabetes mellitus, and chronic kidney disease were reported.

NEWS Post Implementation

Demographic Data

Sepsis screens were completed on 4,349 oncology patients in the study setting who met the inclusion criteria for this project. Duplicates and erroneous records dismissed 467. The inclusion criteria excluded another 3,720 of a NEWS score of 6 or greater. Of the remaining records, 136 were excluded as the record did not have a matching 4 hour before entry; thus, 26 records were included in the data analysis.

Hospital records of patients admitted during this same time, but in 2014, were also reviewed to identify patients who had an ICD 9 diagnosis code of sepsis during their admission. Two hundred forty-nine records were excluded as coded in error or were not in the study location selected. Of the remaining 73 records, 41 did not meet the inclusion criteria of a calculated score of 6 or > and thus 32 records were included in the analysis.

The analysis for this study included 58 sepsis patients, with 32 patients in a pre-NEWS group and 26 in post-NEWS group who had scores of 6 or greater on the NEWS tool at the time of the sepsis alert. Demographic characteristics, disease features, and NEWS scores and categories of the two groups are noted in Table 5. There was a statistical difference in age between the two groups. The pre-NEWS had a mean patient age of 67 years ($SD = 17$) in the Pre-NEWS and 55 years ($SD = 14$) at post-NEWS. Both groups had a preponderance of males than females, with 66% in the pre-NEWS group and 73% in the post-NEWS group ($p = 0.54$); however, there were no statistical differences noted.

Table 5

Demographic Comparison of Patients under Study, Pre- and Post-implementation of the NEWS Tool (n = 58)

	Pre-NEWS <i>n</i> = 32		Post-NEWS <i>n</i> = 26		<i>p</i> ^a
	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Freq (%)	<i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Freq (%)	
Age	66.84 (17.24)		55.39 (13.86)		< .008
Gender					< .54
Male		21 (65.6)		19 (73.1)	
Female		11 (34.4)		7 (26.9)	
Cancer Type					
Leukemia		0 (0)		6 (23.1)	< .004
Neoplasm		30 (93.8)		15 (57.7)	< .001
BMT		0 (0)		1 (3.8)	< .263
Sarcoma		0 (0)		1 (3.8)	< .263
Lymphoma		2 (6.3)		6 (23.1)	< .065
Mortality		9 (28.1)		5 (19.2)	<.543 <.076
Overall Sepsis Category (by NEWS Score)					
SIRS (0-2)		-		-	-
Sepsis (3-5)		-		-	-
Sepsis, Severe (6+)		22 (68.8)		23 (88.5)	
Septic Shock (6+ & SBP <90)		10 (31.3)		3 (11.5)	
Calculated NEWS Score	9.09 (2.74)		7.77 (2.22)		<.051
Infection sub-categories					
Any line sepsis		8 (25)		0 (0)	<.006
PNA		16 (50.0)		5 (19.2)	< .027
Bacteremia		15 (46.9)		4 (15.4)	< .005
Neutropenic		7 (21.9)		6 (23.1)	1.000
Co-Morbidity					
COPD		0 (0)		4 (15.4)	< .035
CHF		1 (3.1)		0 (0.0)	1.000
HTN		13 (40.6)		4 (15.4)	< .046
DM2		9 (28.1)		1 (3.8)	< .017
CKD		7 (21.9)		6 (23.1)	< .913
APACHE 11 Score					<.012 **
High Risk		13 (40.6)		3 (11.5)	-
Low Risk		4 (12.5)		1 (3.8)	-
Not collected		15 (46.9)		22 (84.6)	-
MASCC Risk					1.000
Low		7 (21.9)		6 (23.1)	
High		0 (0)		0 (0)	-
Not collected		25 (78.1)		20 (76.9)	

Note. ^apresented for independent samples *t* tests or chi-square tests of independence;

*cbc, cmp, empiric antibiotics and change if microbiology positive, pro-time, lactic acid, IV fluids, IV fluid bolus, q15 min vital signs mg, and phos.

Cancer Types

Cancer types were also reviewed, and, overall, the post-NEWS had a greater percentage of patients with leukemia 23%, lymphoma 23%, BMT 4%, and sarcoma 4% than did the pre-NEWS group who represented fewer cancer types. There were 0% patients for leukemia, BMT, and sarcoma in the pre-NEWS group. Thirty patients (94%) in the pre-NEWS group had neoplasm compared to 58% in the post-NEWS group and were statistically statistically different with a $p = 0.001$. Likewise, a statistically significant difference ($p < .004$) was noted between the pre and post-NEWS group for leukemia.

Mortality was featured as an integral part of this study to determine if the post-NEWS protocol resulted in fewer mortalities than the non-protocol pre-NEWS group. Nine (28%) pre-NEWS group died within 28 days of hospitalization compared to 5 (19%) in the post-NEWS group; however, the results were not significantly different ($p < .543$).

Sepsis Category

In addition to the nurse NEWS score entered into the data collection spread sheet, a “computer calculated sepsis score” was generated for post-NEWS patients. The 2014 pre-NEWS group were selected by ICD-9 codes for sepsis and assigned a computer programmed “calculated sepsis score” based on the vital sign entry for that septic occurrence. For the purpose of this data analysis, the “computer calculated score” was used. The results showed very little difference between the severe sepsis, coded category 3, and septic shock, coded category 4. Of those coded 3, “severe sepsis” in the data entry, there were 89% post-NEWS compared to 69% pre-NEWS. Septic shock was

coded category 4 (in the data entry) and had 31% pre-NEWS and 12% post-NEWS. The calculated mean scores for the pre-NEWS was 9 ($SD = 2.74$) and the post-NEWS, 8 ($SD = 2.22$). A $p = 0.076$ showed no significance between the categories.

Infection Sub-Categories

To assess if there was a difference between the infection categories, the following variables were analyzed: any central or other line sepsis, PNA, bacteremia and neutropenia. The pre-NEWS group overall had more episodes of infection, and central or other line sepsis ($p = 0.006$), PNA ($p = 0.027$), and bacteremia ($p = 0.005$) were all statistically significant at $p < 0.01$. Neutropenia was uniformly encountered in both the pre-NEWS 22% and post-NEWS 23% group. The most documented source of infection was PNA at 50% pre-NEWS and Neutropenia at 23% post-NEWS.

Co-Morbidity

The most predominant comorbid conditions were hypertension at 41% and DM2 at 28% in the pre-NEWS group with $p = 0.046$ and $p = 0.017$, respectively, statistically significant at $p < 0.01$. In the post-NEWS sample, no statistical differences were noted for CHF (0%) or CKD (6%), although clinically the post-NEWS were 10 years younger. HTN at 41% featured as the most predominant finding pre-NEWS and CKD at 23% post-NEWS.

APACHE 11 and MASCC Risk Scores

APACHE 11 measures the severity of illness in a patient in the ICU setting, and the MASCC scores are used as a measure of stability for neutropenic patients in an ambulatory setting. It is also used in an acute care setting to assess the degree of clinical stability (e.g., if the patient is at risk to go to the ICU). The APACHE 11 high risk scores

pre-NEWS at 41% vs. post-NEWS at 12% and those at a low risk pre-NEWS at 13% vs. post-NEWS at 4% with a $p = 0.012$ were statistically significant at $p < .01$. The low MASCC Scores differed by one patient with the pre-NEWS at 22% compared to 23% post-NEWS.

Time to Treatment

One of the primary outcome measures for this quality improvement study as shown in Table 6, was the effect of the NEWS on time to treatment. In under 60 minutes, 47% were pre-NEWS and 50% were post-NEWS. Treatment after 60 minutes but under 120 minutes occurred in 44% pre-NEWS and 50% post-NEWS. Interventions occurring after 120 minutes but less than 180 minutes occurred in 3 pre-NEWS and 0% post-NEWS. The $p = 0.274$ showed no statistical difference at $p < 0.01$.

Table 6

Time to Treatment and Adherence to Protocol (n = 58)

	Pre-NEWS <i>n</i> = 32 Freq (%)	Post-NEWS <i>n</i> = 26 Freq (%)	<i>p</i> ^a
Time to Treatment			<.274
< 60 mins	15 (46.9)	13 (50.0)	
> 60 or < 120 mins	14 (43.8)	13 (50.0)	
>120 minutes or <180 minutes	3 (9.4)	0 (0)	-
All Protocol Met*			
< 60 mins	15 (46.9)	13 (50.0)	<.813
	Other Interventions		
Lactic Acid	11 (34.4)	6 (23.1)	<.347
IV fluid bolus	16 (50.0)	8 (30.8)	<.139
Repeat IV fluid bolus	16 (50.0)	8 (30.8)	<.139
Every 15 mins VS	11 (34.4)	6 (23.1)	<.347

Note. ^apresented for Independent Samples t-tests or Chi-Square Tests of Independence
*cbc, cmp, mg, phos, empiric antibiotics and change if microbiology positive, pro-time, lactic acid, IV fluids, IV fluid bolus and q15 min vital signs.

The time to treatment considered not only the time to complete the bundle components but also which elements were completed within 60 minutes (see Figure 4). With respect to the protocol components, those with 100% adherence in both the pre-NEWS and post-NEWS groups were complete blood count (CBC), complete metabolic panel (CMP), blood cultures (BCs), empiric antibiotics and change if positive microbiology, pro-time (PT), magnesium (Mg), and phosphorus (Phos). For the remainder of the protocol elements, twice as much adherence occurred pre-NEWS compared to post-NEWS. Lactic acid adherence was 34% (11) in the pre-NEWS group and 23% (6) in the post-NEWS group. IV fluid bolus(s) was 50% (16) in the pre-NEWS group, compared to 31% (8) in the post-NEWS. The q15 min vital signs were predominantly collected in the pre-NEWS 34% (11) vs. the post-NEWS group 23% (6). The differences between the two groups were not significant at $p < 0.01$ (Appendix B).

Figure 4. Time to treatment.

Comparison of NEWS Score Category and Individual NEWS Parameters Values

The 2014 vital signs from the patients' records of those with an ICD-9 code was entered into a pre-constructed data collection tool that included the physiological components of the NEWS tool. A score of 0 to 3 in order of increasing severity, was assigned to each parameter (temperature, pulse, respiration, systolic blood pressure, oxygen saturation, oxygen, and level of consciousness). The cumulative total of the scores for each parameter was entered, and a calculated NEWS score formulated. In addition to the paper protocol NEWS tool score, the 2015 sample was assigned a calculated NEWS score.

NEWS Categories

The total NEWS value, was further categorized into SIRS, sepsis, severe sepsis and septic shock. The results showed that for this sample of oncology patients, sepsis was detected at a score of 6 or higher which is category 3 (severe sepsis), and if the score was a 6 or higher with a systolic blood pressure less than 90, then it was a category 4 (septic shock).

A chi square test of independence revealed that after implementation of the NEWS protocol, there was no statistically significant change in sepsis stage upon detection $p = 0.073$ and not significant at $p < .001$. Surprisingly, after implementation of the NEWS protocol, patients were significantly more likely to be diagnosed with sepsis in late stages (severe sepsis and septic-shock). After implementation, all patients identified had either severe sepsis or were in septic shock (see Table 7 and illustrated in Figure 5). A higher percentage of pre-NEWS subjects 13%, were diagnosed with severe sepsis or septic shock (based on NEWS scoring) than 11.5% post-NEWS patients.

Table 7

Comparison of 2014 and 2015 Calculated NEWS Categories and Individual Parameter Scores

	2014 <i>n</i> = 32 <i>n</i> (%)	Post-NEWS 2015 <i>n</i> = 26 <i>n</i> (%)	<i>p</i> ^a
NEWS SCORE Category			<.073
6 or > (Category 3)	22 (68.8)	23 (88.5)	
6 or > SBP < 90 (Category 4)	10 (31.3)	3 (11.5)	
NEWS Individual Parameters and Parameter Score Values (01,2,3)			
Temp			<.284
T 36.1 - 38	23 (71.9)	13 (50.0)	
T 35 - 39	6 (18.8)	9 (34.6)	
T > 39	3 (9.4)	3 (11.5)	
T < 35	0 (0)	1 (3.8)	
Pulse			<.160
P 51 - 90	3 (9.4)	4 (15.4)	
P 41 - 110	17 (53.1)	9 (34.6)	
P 111 - 130	11 (34.4)	8 (30.8)	
P <41 - > 130	1 (3.1)	5 (19.2)	
Respirations			<.060
R 12 - 20	12 (37.5)	13 (50)	
R 12 - 20	12 (37.5)	13 (50)	
R 9 - 11	0 (0)	0 (0)	
R 21 - 24	6 (18.8)	9 (34.6)	
R < 9 - > 24	14 (43.8)	4 (15.4)	
SBP			<.093
SBP 111 - 220	8 (25)	13 (50.0)	
SBP 101 - 110	5 (15.6)	6 (23.1)	
SBP 90 - 100	9 (28.1)	4 (15.4)	
SBP < 90 - > 220	10 (31.3)	3 (11.5)	
Oxygen Saturation			>.058
S02 > 96%	16 (50.0)	8 (30.8)	
S02 94% - 95%	8 (25.0)	3 (11.5)	
S02 92% - 93%	3 (9.4)	9 (34.6)	
S02 < 92%	5 (15.6)	6 (23.1)	
Level of consciousness			>.061
ALOC	15 (46.9)	6 (23.1)	
Alert	17 (53.1)	20 (76.9)	
Oxygen			<.000
Yes	29 (90.6)	18 (69.2)	
No	3 (9.4)	8 (30.8)	

Note. ^aReported for chi-square tests of independence; ^bInferential statistics cannot be calculated, as variable was a constant.

Figure 5. 2014 and 2015 parameter and sepsis category scores.

NEWS Tool Parameters

The $p = 0.284$ was not for the temperature components at any scoring level. A score of 0 occurred in 72% pre-NEWS vs. 50% post-NEWS. Comparative temperature scores corresponding to a level of 35%, 12%, and 4% were higher in the post-NEWS group. The most frequently occurring score was 0 in 72% pre-NEWS and 50% post-NEWS.

A pulse score of 1 occurred in 53% pre-NEWS compared to 35% post-NEWS. A score of 3 was experienced by 19% post-NEWS compared to 3% pre-NEWS. The predominant score was 2 in both groups, with the findings of 53% pre-NEWS and 35% post-NEWS.

A comparative review of respirations at a score of 0 was found in 50% of the post-NEWS and 38% pre-NEWS. The most common score was 3 in 44% pre-NEWS and 0 which represented 50% post-NEWS. The $p = 0.060$ was not significant at $p < .01$.

In the pre-NEWS sample, 28% of the systolic blood pressure scores were at level 2; at level 3, there were 31% compared to post-NEWS which had 15% and 12%, respectively. The most frequent score in the pre-NEWS was a 3 in 31% and 0 in 50% of the post-NEWS. The $p = 0.093$ was not significant at $p < 0.01$.

Oxygen saturation scores 0 and 1 in the pre-NEWS group represented 50% and 25%, respectively, compared to 31% and 12%, respectively, post NEWS. A score of 2 was seen by 35% and a score of 3 obtained by 23% post-NEWS compared to 9% and 16% pre-NEWS group, respectively. The $p = 0.058$ was not significant at $p > .01$.

More than twice as many in the pre-NEWS sample (47%) were altered compared to post-NEWS sample (23%). The alert variable was predominant in both samples, 53% pre-NEWS and 77% in the post-NEWS. The $p = 0.061$ was not significant at $p > 0.01$.

Oxygen use was predominantly found in the pre-NEWS sample (91%) compared to the post-NEWS sample (69%). The $p = 0.000033$ was significant at $p < 0.01$.

Mortality and Time to Treatment

The data attempted to analyze the time to treatment and mortality due to the NEWS intervention is shown in Table 8. The sample size for mortality in the pre-NEWS was 28% in the pre-NEWS group and 19% in the post-NEWS group. The pre-NEWS group achieved a time to treatment of 89% in under 60 minutes, with 11% in 60 minutes but under the 120-minute group. Lactic acid and q15 minute vital signs were obtained in 56% of patients and intravenous fluids with a repeat bolus in 89% of the pre-NEWS group (Figure 6).

The post-NEWS group had a 100% adherence to all bundle components. The relationship between program implementation, timely administration of the treatment

bundle, and their interaction effect on 28-day sepsis mortality could not be examined with a multiple logistic regression model due to small sample size.

Table 8

*Mortality and Time to Treatment and Adherence to Protocol by Percentage
(n = 14)*

	Pre-NEWS Mortality <i>n</i> = 9; Freq (%)	Post-NEWS Mortality <i>n</i> = 5; Freq (%)
Time to Treatment		
< 60 mins	8 (88.9)	5 (100)
> 60 or < 120 mins	1 (11.1)	0 (0)
>120 minutes or <180 minutes	0 (0)	0 (0)
All Protocol Met		
< 60 mins	1 (11.1)	5 (100)
Lactic Acid	5 (55.6)	5 (100)
IV fluid bolus	8 (88.9)	5 (100)
Repeat IV fluid bolus	8 (88.9)	5 (100)
Q15 mins vs	5 (55.6)	5 (100)
Sepsis Category		
SIRS (0-2)	-	-
Sepsis (3-5)	-	-
Sepsis, Severe (6+)	8 (88.9)	4 (80)
Septic Shock (6+ and SBP < 90)	1 (11.1)	1 (20)

Figure 6. Mortality, time to treatment and adherence to the bundle components.

Four Hours Before Calculated and Final Nurse Score 2015 Data

The purpose of this data was to determine if there is a difference in the 4-hours before NEWS data and the final nurse scores. A paired *t* test was applied to the 4 hours prior data and the final data as illustrated in Table 9. For both groups $n = 26$, the 4 hours before M was 7.9 with a SD of 1.59. The final M was 7.77 with a SD 2.2. This two-tailed test had a value of $p < .796$ (95%: CI 1.03-1.37). The Fisher exact test statistic value was 0.465. The result was not significant at $p > .01$. Overall, there is no statistical difference between the 4H before and the final data in 2015. Clinically, this was significant, as it indicates 77% cases of severe sepsis and 15% cases of septic shock were not detected as having sepsis 4 hours earlier (see Table 9 and illustrated in Figure 7).

Table 9

Comparison of 4 Hours Calculated and Final NEWS Score Data for 2015 (n = 26)

	2015 n = 26 n (%) Four Hours Prior	2015 n = 26 n (%) Final	p ^a
Mean (Standard Deviation)	7.932 (1.59)	7.769 (2.20)	<.796 ^a
NEWS Categories			<.456 ^b
6 or > (Category 3)	20 (76.9)	23 (88.5)	
6 or > SBP < 90 (Category 4)	4 (15.3)	3 (11.5)	
NEWS Individual Parameters and Parameter Score Values (01,2,3)			
Temp			
T 36.1 - 38	13 (50.0)	13 (50.0)	
T 35 - 39	9 (34.6)	9 (34.6)	
T > 39	3 (11.5)	3 (11.5)	
T < 35	1 (3.8)	1 (3.8)	
Pulse			
P 51 - 90	4 (15.4)	4 (15.4)	
P 41 - 110	8 (30.8)	9 (34.6)	
P 111 - 130	9 (34.6)	8 (30.8)	
P < 41 - > 130	5 (19.2)	5 (19.2)	
Respirations			
R 12 - 20	14 (54.9)	13 (50)	
R 9 - 11	0 (0)	0 (0)	
R 21 - 24	7 (26.9)	9 (34.6)	
R < 9 - > 24	14 (15.4)	4 (15.4)	
SBP			
SBP 111 - 220	12 (46.2)	13 (50.0)	
SBP 101 - 110	6 (23.1)	6 (23.1)	
SBP 90 - 100	5 (19.2)	4 (15.4)	
SBP < 90 - > 220	3 (11.5)	3 (11.5)	
Oxygen Saturation			
S02 > 96%	8 (30.8)	8 (30.8)	
S02 94% - 95%	5 (19.2)	3 (11.5)	
S02 92% - 93%	8 (30.8)	9 (34.6)	
S02 < 92%	5 (19.2)	6 (23.1)	
Level of consciousness			
ALOC	6 (23.1)	6 (23.1)	
Alert	20 (76.9)	20 (76.9)	
Oxygen			
Yes	19 (73.1)	18 (69.2)	
No	7 (26.9)	8 (30.8)	

Note. ^aNEWS score paired *t* test; ^bNEWS category scores Fisher exact test.

Figure 7. Four hours before the final NEWS category and parameter scores.

A Comparison of Correctly Calculated NEWS Scores with the Nurses' Report 2015 Data

NEWS Nurse Scores

There were 26 NEWS nurse scores and 26 NEWS calculated nurse scores presented in this correlational table based upon 2015 post-NEWS data (Table 10). The range of the scores was 6 to 11 in the nurse NEWS score and 6 to 16 in the NEWS calculated score. The nurses NEWS score correlated with the calculated nurse score 50% (13) of the time. A further examination of the variances displayed 1 was scored higher and 12 was scored lower. Of the 12 scored lower, the $M = 2.5$ ($SD = 1.38$). These results were not submitted for chi-square analysis.

NEWS Category Scores

From an analysis of those in the higher categories, the nurse NEWS categories, 1 (3.8%) was in category 4, but according to the nurse NEWS category, the patient was a

category 3. The lower categories had 54%. Of these, 31% were in a category 2 but were actually a category 3, and 15% were classified as category 1 but were a category 3. Of significance to this project, 1 (3.8%) was placed in category 1 but was actually a category 4, and 1 (3.8%) was a category 2 but was actually a category 4. Thus in a sample of 26 post-NEWS patients, 7.6% were potentially affected by a lower nurse score. These results were not presented for chi-square analysis (see Table 10 and illustrated in Figure 8).

Table 10

Comparison of Correctly Calculated NEWS Scores with Nurses Report 2015 data (n = 26)

	NEWS Score Nurse n = 26	NEWS Score Calculated n = 26	x/SD
NEWS Nurse Scores *			
Range of scores	6 to 11	6 to 16	
Range of scores differences	1 - 4		
Correct scores	13 (50%)		
Nurse NEWS score higher and amount	1 (1%)***		
Nurse NEWS score lower and amount	12 (46%)		2.5 (1.38)
NEWS Nurse Category score**			
Higher category			
Cat 4--->3		1 (3.8%)	
Lower category			
Cat 2--->3		14 (53.8%)	
Cat 1--->3		8 (30.8%)	
Cat 1--->4		4(15.4%)	
Cat 1--->4		1(3.8%)	
Cat 2--->4		1(3.8%)	

Note. *Nurse score from the paper protocol; ** Nurse' News Category refers to SIRS (category 1), sepsis (category 2), severe sepsis (category 3), and shock (category 4).

*** Stayed in the same category.

Figure 8. Nurses NEWS score compared to the calculated final nurse report.

DISCUSSION

From this analysis of the results, this quality improvement project attempted to answer the following questions. The first question was, *What impact did age, diagnosis, and co-morbidities have on NEWS?* This analysis looked at the effects of age, cancer type, infection, co-morbidities, NEWS scores, and categories on mortality. The post-NEWS group was, on average, 10 years younger than the comparison group, had fewer patients suffering from HTN or DM2 (though more had COPD), and had different cancer profiles than the comparison group (who almost exclusively had neoplasms) which may have impacted the results. Additional risk factors for mortality in patients receiving cytotoxic therapies was identified by Thursky and Worth (2015) and included neutropenic sepsis, MASCC score of less than 21, hematological malignancy, and bacteremia. Of the two groups, the pre-NEWS had more patients with neutropenia, bacteremia, category 4 septic shock, and high risk APACHE 11 scores. Although hematological malignancy was more prevalent in the post-NEWS group, this group had less risk factors already discussed. From this analysis of the risk profiles associated with mortality, the pre-NEWS group appears to carry the higher risk for mortality independent of a nurse driven protocol.

The second question postulated, *Was implementation of the NEWS protocol associated with a change in patient treatment (specifically time to treatment)?* The research question attempts to address the activation of NEWS tool and treatment bundle and the effect on the time treatment for both the pre-NEWS and post-NEWS. As noted by Buist et al. (2002), standardized nursing assessment tools that link physiologic parameters with specific nursing actions such as the NEWS can improve the early

identification and rescue of patients clinically deteriorating outside the ICU by employing a consistent assessment tool by nurses regardless of experience.

From the results shown in Table 6, the medical assessment team response and nurse driven protocol for a NEWS score of 6 or > reduced the time to treatment in 50% of the post-NEWS group compared to 47% in the pre-NEWS group, the $p = 0.274$ which was not significant at $p > .01$. Although the time to treatment is slightly biased in favor of the protocol group, other questions need to be addressed, such as adherence to all the bundle components in the post-NEWS group. After accounting for 100% adherence in the pre- and post-NEWS group for other components (blood cultures, complete blood count, empiric antibiotics, and change if positive cultures, magnesium, and phosphorus), compliance to the lactic acid component was noted to be 23% in post-NEWS compared to 34% pre-NEWS. Lactic acid levels as part of this bundle protocol was used because of the relationship to organ dysfunction in sepsis. Other concerns included IV fluid bolus(es) which was administered to 31% post-NEWS compared to 50% pre-NEWS and the q15mins vital signs which were 23% post-NEWS compared to 34% pre-NEWS. Overall, an opportunity to treat a patient in under 1 hour for severe sepsis or shock was missed in 50% of cases, and the reasons were multifactorial and are discussed further.

Upon further analysis of these two groups, all the pre-NEWS groups received treatment in the ICU compared to the post-NEWS, who were treated on the floor. It can be postulated that the ICU patients were seen and treated more expediently than the floor patients prior to a nurse driven protocol. Conversely, the implementation of the post-NEWS medical assessment team (MAT) response required a considerable cultural change throughout the hospital with an extensive amount of manual labor required for the data

collection by the nurses on paper handouts. The lack of provider (Medical Doctors (MDs), Nurse Practitioners (NPs) and Registered Nurses(RNs) orientation to the NEWS tool and protocol may have played role. A brief 6-question orientation was given to the RNs utilizing an online education forum, and the NP and MD received a verbal rendition from the lead sepsis committee RN. The lack of consistency with documentation was also apparent when inputting data from the paper protocol sheets to the data collection tool. Multiple errors in NEWS scores were found, duplicate records, incorrect scores, and partially tallied scores on the protocol sheets. Thus, the knowledge was inadequate and implementation was not consistent by the day and night nurses. Inadequate knowledge of the protocol could negatively impact treatment, resulting in a delay of IV fluid bolus(es), q15mins vitals and lactic acid levels. A lack of expertise on behalf of the provider and/or the RN could also be a confounding variable. The medical wards were chosen for this project, as the nurses in those areas are the primary responders to deterioration. Floor nurses, however, are unaccustomed to managing a clinically deteriorating patient. This process of following the treatment bundle may have been an overwhelming process for some, and a lack of familiarity with all the protocol requirements and expertise managing a patient without a physician or nurse practitioner present may have affected the care and delayed the treatment of this septic patient. The implications for practice that have evolved from these results was to ensure all providers were adequately informed about a process improvement project, in particular a project that could have a significant impact on the life of a patient.

The third question asked, *Was implementation of the NEWS protocol associated with a change in detected sepsis category (specifically early stage detection)?* The

researcher also wanted to identify a difference between the 2014 vital sign data and the NEWS tool data. The NEWS tool is a physiological tool utilized to improve patient outcomes in cardiac arrests (Smith et al., 2013). The tool was adapted for this quality improvement study based on a preliminary pilot study in November 2014 during which a score of 7 was determined to be too high for sepsis detection, and thus, the cumulative score was adjusted to 6 to detect neutropenic septic patients. Both groups were assigned a calculated score based upon the NEWS tool. The results showed a good correlation between the two groups with no significant differences. The relative contribution of individual physiological markers for the detection of sepsis in an oncology population was presented in Table 3. A chi-square analysis did show that after implementation of the NEWS protocol, more patients (89%, $n = 23$) were categorized in severe sepsis compared to 69% ($n = 22$) pre-implementation. Conversely, more patients had septic shock pre-implementation (31%, $n = 10$) compared to 12% ($n = 3$) post-implementation. The latter may be accounted for by more expeditious treatment of the patient post-NEWS prior to being transferred to the ICU compared to the pre-NEWS group who had not received prior treatment on the floor.

Further inspection of the parameters' temperature, pulse, respirations, systolic blood pressure, oxygen saturation, and level of consciousness at the levels 0 to 3 showed uniformity in the overall results. Oxygen use was a prominent feature with 91% ($n = 29$) in the 2014 pre-NEWS data and 69% ($n = 18$) in the 2015 post-NEWS. The p -value $<.000$, indicates significance at $p <.01$ level.

The fourth question was, *What impact did NEWS and the treatment bundle have on sepsis mortality rates in the pre-NEWS group vs. the post-NEWS group?* Project

results identified less mortality in the post-NEWS group and suggested that after adjustment for age, severity of illness, and co-morbidities, early treatment of septic patients with a nurse driven protocol can have a positive impact on mortality. There were three times as many deaths in the pre-NEWS as the Post-NEWS; 5 patients died post-NEWS and 9 died pre-NEWS. More post-NEWS patients (89%) were in the severe sepsis category than the pre-NEWS patients (69%). In the shock category, 31% were in the pre-NEWS compared to 12% post-NEWS. All pre-NEWS patients went to the ICU with a code of sepsis, but only those in shock went to the ICU in the post-NEWS groups. Thus, it can be postulated that early treatment interventions on the floor, such as a nurse driven treatment and bundle protocol can reduce mortality. This result concurs with Levy et al. (2010) who identified treatment bundles resulted in a 16% reduction in the in-hospital absolute mortality rate in septic patients compared to control subjects receiving standard care. Although this researcher would like to credit the nurse driven protocol with the achievement of the lower mortality, other confounding variables need to be discussed. One such factor is nurse expertise. The ICU nurses are familiar with care of clinically deteriorating patients and were given an in-service on the nurse driven protocol. Conversely, the pre-NEWS group ICU nurses were not practicing according to a protocol and dependent on the MD/NP practitioners to enter the information which resulted in delay of care and possibly more patient deaths. These differences could also be attributable due to the post-NEWS group being significantly younger and having less infection categories and comorbidities than the pre-NEWS group.

The fifth question was, *What effect does 4 hours before and the final NEWS scores have on the NEWS categories?* For each vital sign entry in the 2015 post-NEWS

data, a corresponding 4 hours before data entry was obtained from the medical records and a calculated NEWS score assigned to each physiological parameter according to the NEWS tool scoring values. The results displayed in Table 8 indicate an average score of 8 on both the pre-NEWS and post-NEWS calculated scores. The sepsis categories showed very little variance and no statistical significance; however, the implications to practice suggest that 20 cases in severe sepsis and 4 cases in septic shock were a missed opportunity to initiate the treatment bundle earlier. This quality improvement project recognized the contributions of the Surviving Sepsis Campaign (SSC), formed in 2002 to reduce sepsis by 25% in 5 years. As mentioned in a review of practices by Durthaler, Ernst, and Johnson (2009), the guideline proposed 17 recommendations; the three most frequently mentioned of importance were obtaining blood cultures, administration of broad spectrum antibiotics, and anticoagulation. Of relevance to this discussion was the basic care bundle elements which included the rapid delivery of intravenous fluids and the administration of intravenous antibiotics within 1 hour, which can reduce mortality by 30% to 50% (Daniels et al., 2011). The logistics of planning the data collection for the appointed vital sign time was a monumental task for these medical floor nurses with very little orientation and would have presented a significant burden to document and respond to 4-hours before data.

Question six asked, *What was the degree of concordance/discordance between the nurses' NEWS categories/score and the NEWS calculated categories/scores?*

Examination of Table 10 shows NEWS scores calculated from official records of patients' vitals compared to the NEWS scores reported by nurses, revealed that nurses only corrected calculated and reported NEWS scores 50% of the time (13 of 26 NEWS

scores). When nurses reported the wrong NEWS score, it was far more likely to be reported at a lower score 54% of the time (14 of 26 NEWS scores) than as a higher score. Only 1 patient actually warranted a lower score than was given (3.8% of the time; 1 of 26 NEWS scores). As revealed in the results, not only did the nurse-reported NEWS scores frequently underestimate actual NEWS scores, but the deviations were substantial, yielding up to 5 points lower on the NEWS scale, a deviation large enough to take a patient from the lowest risk category (NEWS = 0-2) to the most severe category septic shock (NEWS 6 > + SBP < 90).

In this sample of 26 post-NEWS patients, nurses' compliance with the correct NEWS tool score was 50%. Nurses scored the NEWS tool lower in 46% cases and 1 case was scored higher. This sample of 13 patients which represents 50% of the total under review can be regarded as a "missed" opportunity to provide treatment to a severely septic patient, due to human error. Although this sample size was too small to generalize, the results provided valuable insight into the ramifications of human errors due to data entry by a paper protocol and the impact these errors can have on patient treatment.

Implications for Practice

Although the paper protocol entries were time consuming for the nurses, this process was a key method by which to identify septic patients. However of the total number of 4,349 records collected, 3,720 records (85%) were rejected due to errors in documentation. This suggests that if this project is to be repeated, a person needs to be assigned to check the scores during each 12-hour shift. A thorough knowledge of the project by all clinicians could have had a significant impact. Education prior to and post

study may have yielded a difference in knowledge prior to and after implementation. Finally, by practical experience, the RNs were more aware of sepsis detection and treatment due to the nurse driven protocol and bundle, but as already mentioned, these patients were picked at the later stages of sepsis.

Strengths

This study had a number of strengths. Based on the author's review of literature, this was the first study to utilize the NEWS tool with a septic oncology population and is an initial step in optimizing the sepsis screening process. The process of going through this quality improvement project was extremely challenging and time consuming but an empowering process for the nurses to see the end result of their endeavors. The project was beneficial to the field of nursing, and, overall, there was a positive change in the organization as a result of the NEWS and treatment bundle. Specific contributions were the following: There was a decrease in mortality in the post-NEWS sample by 19% which was above the expected goal predicted for the medical center of 10%; neutropenic septic patients with higher incidences of hypertension and type 2 diabetes who are older than 65 years may be at greater risk of death from sepsis; education and adequate preparation of staff prior to a project intervention is essential; and oxygen use in the pre- and post-NEWS groups was identified as a predominant indicator in severe sepsis and shock.

Limitations

This was a retrospective case study involving chart reviews of pre and post implementation samples. The samples were not matched by age, size, cancer type, or infection. Ideally, it would have been more efficacious for the two pre and post samples

to be matched in every way. However, due to the predominant focus which was sepsis, this researcher was concerned about an adequate sample size for both groups. Selection bias, variations in sepsis detection, diagnostic lab tests, and treatments threaten the internal validity of the studies. The before-and-after design of the studies may also subject the differences found between patients in the pre and post implementation groups to confounding factors that can occur with temporal changes. Furthermore, there were differences among the sepsis protocols received by each patient which could potentially affect prognosis. It can be implied from the 4-hours before data that patients can still develop severe sepsis or shock independent of the treatment bundles due to confounding variables, and thus, the results may not be generalized.

Conclusions

Time to treatment was positively influenced by a NEWS tool and standardized order set but more education was needed to ensure all providers were educated on the goals of the project. There was room for improvement, as the treatment bundle requirements were only met in 50% of the sample. The decreased mortality in the post-NEWS groups also suggests that implementation of treatment on the floor can minimize mortality if sepsis is treated earlier. Potential barriers to successful implementation and adherence to the sepsis guidelines were deficient knowledge among clinicians regarding the evidence-based guidelines for the detection and treatment of sepsis. An interesting finding was that 4-hour data prior to the final NEWS score missed septic patients that potentially could have received treatment earlier. It is speculation at best to suggest that progression into septic shock and ICU admission could have been prevented. Substantial human errors were made with entries into the paper protocols which can

potentially delay treatment and affect patient outcomes. This was found by the investigator during the initial data entry with the exclusion of several thousand records. The implications to practice have already been acknowledged by leadership at the medical center who are making plans to install a computer-generated sepsis application to detect a sepsis alert immediately. This will allow more accurate data analysis and allow the comparison between variables immediately, thereby hastening the interventions. This should enable the scoring mechanism to be fine-tuned to ensure the weighting of each of the sepsis categories is appropriate.

Additionally, it was determined that a NEWS score of 6 was capturing patients in late stage sepsis (severe sepsis and septic shock) rather than in sepsis. It can be surmised that this is due to the severity of illness of these cancer patients. Chemo-toxic therapies reduce the immune response which alters the patient's threshold to infection. The inclusion of neutropenia, a hematological cancer, and one or more co-morbidities can spiral a patient into severe sepsis very rapidly. Awareness of the shortcoming of this quality improvement project provides insight into how a process can be improved in the future. This project has provided a framework for future studies to rescreen cancer patients at lower NEWS scores with a comparison of the paper protocol results to a calculated NEWS value measured against patient outcomes.

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APPENDIX A

THE NEWS TOOL AND TREATMENT BUNDLE PROTOCOL

Table A: News Tool and Treatment Bundle Protocol

1. 220 Assess patient, VS, and National Early Warning Score (NEWS); Sepsis Screening Score Q shift or PRN							
Vital Signs (Time) _____							
Temp				BP			
HR				MAP			
Respiration				O2 Sat			
Current NEWS Score _____							
NEWS	3	2	1	0	1	2	3
Temp (°C)	< 35		35–36	36.1–38	38.1–39	> 39	
Pulse (bpm)	< 41		41–50	51–90	91–110	111–130	> 130
Resp (bpm)	< 9		9–11	12–20		21–24	> 24
SBP (mmHg)	< 90	90–100	101–110	111–220			> 220
SO ₂	< 92%	92–93%	94–95%	> 96%			
Oxygen		YES		NO			
LOC				ALERT			ALOC
2. If a patient's NEWS score is > 6, immediately assess patient, call MAT team at 77, and notify primary team.							
CONSIDERATIONS prior to calling MAT team: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Palliative Care/DNR • Expected SE of Chemotherapy/Biotherapy 					<input type="checkbox"/>		
MAT team notification							
Time _____							
Primary team notification							
Time _____							
3. Once MAT team is called, anticipate initiation of the following interventions*:							
*MUST BE DONE WITHIN ONE HOUR							

	<p>OTHER TESTS TO CONSIDER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCVO2 _____ • ABG _____ • EKG _____ • CXR _____ • BLOOD GLUCOSE _____ • UA/C&S _____ 																																			
A. OBTAIN LARGE BORE IV ACCESS _____																																				
B. IMMEDIATE TESTS:																																				
• Two SETS OF BLOOD CULTURES (peripheral + central line) _____																																				
• LACTIC ACID _____																																				
• CBC _____																																				
• CMP/MG/PHOS _____																																				
• PT/INR _____																																				
C. GIVE IV BOLUS (**FLUID RESUSCITATION GOAL: <u>30 ML/KG</u>)	<p>**CONSIDER IV RESUSCITATION IF MAP < 65 AND SBP < 90 *</p> <p>DOCUMENT ANY IV RESUSITATION CONTRAINDICATIONS</p>																																			
• NS 500 ML _____																																				
• NS 500 ML _____ (CONSIDER REPEAT IF BP NOT RESPONDING)																																				
D. START BROAD-SPECTRUM ABX OR REVISE ABX REGIMEN																																				
E. VS Q 15 MINUTES																																				
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APPENDIX B

FIGURE: TREATMENT TIME AND BUNDLE COMPONENTS

Figure B. Time to treatment and adherence to bundle components.

APPENDIX C

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Purpose, (Author/s, Year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations, and Notes
<p>To test the sensitivity and specificity of various early scoring systems to predict deterioration in the patient's condition</p> <p>Duckitt, Buxton-Thomas, Walker, Cheek, Bewick, and Forni (2007)</p>	<p>Prospective, observational</p> <p>IV: validation of the Worthing Physiological Scoring System (WPSC)</p> <p>DV: VR, HR, AP, T, O₂ sat, LOC, LOS, STD, CA</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 384 Phase 1 (July and November 2003)</p> <p><i>N</i> = 1102 Phase 2 (October and November 2005)</p> <p>Location: Emergency Admissions Unit (EAU), United Kingdom</p>	<p>Phase 1: All admissions to EAU during the study period</p> <p>Phase 2: Data collection to validate prospectively the WPSC</p> <p>Prognostic variables (PV): VR, HR, AP, T, O₂ sat, LOC</p> <p>Multivariate logistics regression (MLR): hospital mortality</p> <p>PV: Partitioned by O'Brien method and analyzed by MLR</p> <p>Discrimination assessed by AUC</p> <p>Post hoc comparison of the NEWS scores with</p>	<p>MLR: some PV, not statistically significant</p> <p>Final model showed good AUC 0.74 (95% CI 0.71–0.77)</p> <p>RC showed the weighting of PV</p> <p>When the new scoring was applied to validation data, AUC 0.72 (95% CI, 0.66–0.79) was $p = 0.565$ for goodness of fit-</p> <p>The NEWS scoring system was compared to the EWS and was significantly better ($p < 0.001$)</p> <p>A scores of 6 is associated with mortality</p>	<p>This study was the first to link PV with mortality in EAU</p> <p>The NEWS scoring system performed better than did the EWS</p> <p>Study advantage: All demands to construct a new severity of illness score were met</p> <p>The link between WPSC and CA is uncertain due to incomplete data</p> <p>Application to practice: Proposed QI project will assess the relative weight of NEWS to determine early sepsis</p>

			the EWS scores Sig. $p < 0.05$		
Accident and emergency staff perceptions of a PSST utilized by ambulance clinicians Fitzpatrick, McKenna, Beckett, and Pringle (2014)	Descriptive QI project IV: use of PSST sepsis screening tool DV: employee responses to survey	$N = 39$ Online 5-point Likert scale survey responses from registered nurses, medical doctors regarding perceptions of the PSST, and pre-alert systems by ED, AAU, and CAU	Pre-test questionnaire piloted before the OLS Anonymous OLS, demographics, years of service Response to 5-point Likert scale Participants emailed	Responded to the survey by email: 18/39 (46%) = RNs 20/39 (51%) = MDs PSST awareness: 32/39 (82%) PSST improves care: 34/39 (87%) Most agree that PSST can be accurately used by ambulance clinicians Pre-alert one on one: 26/39 (67%) Telephone: 21/39 (54%) Adequacy of the pre-alert: 20/23 (87%)	PSST can be used effectively by ambulance clinicians and, thus, reduce time to treatment High degree of trust between the clinicians Pre-alerts that were the most favorable were by telephone, least was by radio and by one on one, if not communicated clearly Application of practice: Use of a tool to screen patients for severity of illness and reduce time to treatment
The effect of survival in immuno-compromised patients (ICM) versus immune-competent (ICOM) patients at Day 28 in an ICU for severe	Observational prospective IV: immune profile DV: mortality	$N = 1981$ Patients with severe sepsis or septic shock 11 ICUs in	All severe sepsis and shock Immune profile: AIDS, malignancies, infection, organ transplant,	All-cause neutropenia (28%) Non-neutropenia (26.5%) Hematologic malignancy (26.5%)	Sepsis risks were higher in the ICOM patients Immuno-deficiency, such as AIDS, and any malignant disease

<p>sepsis or septic shock</p> <p>Tolsma, Schwebel, Azoulay, Darmon, Souweine, Vesin, . . . Timsit (2013)</p>		<p>France</p> <p>January 1997 through August 2011</p>	<p>hematologic, malignancy, with or without neutropenia</p> <p>MVM to assess all risk factors, subdivision hazards ratio and 95% CI</p>	<p>Profiles associated with higher risk of death: AIDs 95% CI, 1.077–3,408; hematologic malignancy without neutropenia 95% CI, 1.002–1.994; and neutropenia regardless of its cause 95% CI, 1.299–2.224</p>	<p>without neutropenia or a neutropenia, regardless of its cause, was an independent, poor prognostic indicator for survival and was associated with risk of death at Day 28</p> <p>Limitations: Selection of patients was based on diagnostic codes, looked at only ICU patients</p> <p>Application to practice: Neutropenic septic mortality rates of a cohort that will be studied in the proposed doctoral project</p>
<p>Members of a sepsis mortality improvement team (SMITe) developed a sepsis protocol for screening sepsis on medical surgical units</p> <p>Lopez-Bushnell, Demary, and Jaco (2014)</p>	<p>Quality improvement project</p> <p>PDSA model</p> <p>IV: SMITe team</p> <p>DV: mortality due to sepsis</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 225</p> <p>Patients screened positive for sepsis</p> <p>Medical and surgical units at University of New Mexico</p> <p>March 2008 through April 2009</p>	<p>Data collected through chart abstractions and reviewed by SMITe members</p> <p>SMITe was a group of volunteer registered nurses who received a 4-hour inservice on an SSC and one medical doctor</p>	<p>225 patients screened positive for sepsis (10%)</p> <p>Screening reduces mortality to 30%</p> <p>Over a 4-year period, reduced mortality by 50%</p> <p>Nurse satisfaction</p>	<p>Members of a SMITe developed a sepsis protocol for screening sepsis on medical surgical units</p>

				scores increased from 72% to 78%	
To audit the efficacy of a neutropenic clinical pathway Higgins and Hill (2012)	Retrospective Case note analysis, online survey, and questionnaires IV: adherence to national sepsis guidelines DV: time to administration of antibiotic, tumor type, granulocyte colony stimulating factor, temperature, mortality, dose reduction, chemotherapy treatment delay	<i>N</i> = 88 Neutropenic cancer patients on chemotherapy Patients presented to the EDs and medical observation units or oncology units September 2010 to February 2011	3 data collection tools: Case note analysis to identify treatment of the neutropenic pathways Questionnaire mailed to assess knowledge of the staff Questionnaire mailed to patient to assess knowledge and presence of alert card	Case note analysis: Chemo delay 16/60 Dose reduction 6/60 Treatment cessation 8/60 Mortality 2/60 Received abx in one hour 18/79 Staff knowledge: Staff awareness 88% Knowledge of first-line abx 84% Specific training 50% Patient knowledge: Received alert card 89% Understood information 87% Attended ED 30%	To audit the efficacy of a neutropenic clinical pathway
To describe de-escalation of empirical antibiotic treatment in neutropenic patients Mokart, Slehofer, Lambert, Sannini, Chow-Chine, . . . Leone, M. (2014)	Prospective observational IV: de-escalation of antibiotic treatment DV: time to treatment, guideline adherence, mortality	<i>N</i> = 101 Neutropenic patients with severe sepsis or septic shock ICU and cancer ward in hospital in France January 2008 to Mary 2010	Neutropenia < 500 cells/mm ³ Or leukocytes < 1,000 cells/mm ³ Severe sepsis and septic shock defined according to SSC Abxs given as soon as the patient is in the	All de-escalation occurred within 12 days. The SOFA at ICU was similar in the de-escalation group compared to the escalation group The time lapsed	De-escalation was accomplished in 40% of patients and did not affect patient outcomes Neutropenic patients need to be treated until the neutropenia resolves Important to collect

			<p>ICU</p> <p>De-escalation refers to deleting one antibiotic of a combined treatment or narrowing the range based on identified organism</p>	<p>between severe sepsis onset and its ICU management did not reach statistical significant $p = 0.057$</p> <p>The ICU mortality rate was 23%</p> <p>There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups $p = 0.57$</p>	<p>blood cultures per the guidelines to hasten de-escalation of unneeded abx</p> <p>Neutropenic patients respond better to carbapenem with higher rates of de-escalation</p> <p>Application to practice: Neutropenic patients who receive immediate attention regarding abx and blood cultures prior to abx will have faster de-escalation of abx</p>
<p>Validate a scoring system to alert ward staff of worsening clinical condition</p> <p>Cuthbertson, Boroujerdi, Mckie, Aucott, and Prescott (2007)</p>	<p>Retrospective and prospective comparative study</p> <p>IV: screening tool</p> <p>DV: HR, RR, SBP, T, Oxygen sat, urine volume, LOC</p>	<p>$N = 70$</p> <p>Surgical HDU in Scotland</p> <p>Group 1: HDU recruited July 1 through August 15, 2003</p> <p>Group 2: HDU then ICU sequential admissions</p>	<p>Physiologic variables: RR, HR, T, SBP, O₂ sat, LOC, urine volume, LOC, demographics, and surgical diagnosis</p> <p>Median, discriminatory ability with ROC</p> <p>Logistic regression to generate ROC curves and make comparisons between the two groups</p>	<p>The AUCs for Group 1 and Group 2 > HR, RR, and SaO₂ compared to HR, RR, SBP, and SaO₂</p> <p>The variables HR, RR, and SaO₂ have the highest values (AUC = 0.9)</p> <p>Removal of T and SBP had no influence on the magnitude of the results</p>	<p>Discriminant analysis was used to examine individual and combination of variables for example: HR, RR, SBP, Temp, SaO₂, EWS, MEWS, and PART. Cut points represent the maximum sensitivity and specificity for the variable or score and demonstrated higher levels of discriminate power (AUROC > 0.7)</p>

				ICU patients scored significantly higher than HDU in the 24 hours before ICU admission	Fewer variables have superior predictive accuracy versus EWS, MEWS, PART, and MET scores Application to practice: Development of a validated EWS systems is vital to allow the effective, efficient, and cost-effective recognition of the deteriorating patient
To evaluate the associations between risk factors and serious complications in patients presenting to the ED with FN Lynn, Chen, Weng, and Chiu (2013)	Retrospective case-control study IV: Time to abx in FN patients DV: respiratory failure, refractory hypotension, ICU admission, DIC, ALOC, arrhythmias, mortality	<i>N</i> = 81 Chemo-induced FN for underlying malignancy ED at a Medical Center in Taiwan January 2008 to December 2008	Neutropenia defined as absolute neutrophil count < 0.5 x 10 ⁹ /L Fever > 38.3 ^o C at triage or within 24h Continuous variables are presented by median and interquartile range and categorical variables by count and percentage Comparison between groups by the Fisher's exact test and Mann-Whitney for categorical and	Model 1: Univariate logistics regression analyzed variables with <i>p</i> < 0.2, gender, pulse rate ≤ 100, plts < 50,000/mic/l, pna, enterococcus and latency of abx Model 2: Multivariable logistics regression found latency of the first dose of abx in minutes to predict serious complications, followed by pna and plt count 2 variables identified septic shock and	Latency of the first dose of abx, pna, and plt count < 50,000/mm ³ were identified to be independent factors associated with serious complications Earlier administration of abx associated with fewer complications in FN Limitations: restrictive nature of the definition of neutropenia, which excluded other patients between 0.5 and 1 x 10 ⁹ /L

			<p>continuous variables</p> <p>Multivariable models and $p < 0.2$ in logistic regression analyses, ROC for comparison models and $p < 0.05$</p>	<p>mortality in FN: pulmonary infections and elevated serum lactate levels.</p>	<p>Application to practice: My QI project will concern FN patients; this article validates that the timely administration of abx can lead to decreased risk of complications</p>
<p>Comparison of nine prediction scores to estimate risk of clinical deterioration</p> <p>Yu, Leung, Hoe, Soto, Shah, Gunda, and Gong (2014)</p>	<p>Retrospective case-control study</p> <p>IV: validation of risk using screening tools</p> <p>DV: clinical deterioration, mortality, source of infection, comorbidities, sepsis</p>	<p>$N = 328$</p> <p>Diagnosis of infection present on admission</p> <p>ED at a medical center in New York</p> <p>December 1, 2009, and March 31, 2010</p>	<p>Scores were selected if the scoring system modeled risk for deterioration, was validated by AUC (0.7), and consisted of physiologic components readily collected for ward patients</p> <p>Univariate analysis, 2-tailed Fisher exact test, Student <i>t</i>-test, or Wilcoxon rank-sum test was use for analysis of the variables</p> <p>Mixed-effects linear model to determine effects over time and odds ratio</p>	<p>AUC was computed for all time intervals 0–12 hours</p> <p>SOFA AUC 0.78 (95% CI)</p> <p>ViEWS AUC 0.75 (95% CI)</p> <p>MEDS 0.74 (95% CI)</p> <p>MEWS 0.73 (95% CI)</p> <p>Plots of scores and averages on graphs increased closer to the time of deterioration</p> <p>For SOFA detected even earlier (12-24 h before deterioration) $p = .005$</p>	<p>Nine risk prediction scores were tested; 8/9 performed similarly and had acceptable discrimination (AUC > 0.70) within 12 hours prior to clinical deterioration</p> <p>SOFA had increased prognostic value and indicated that ED and ICU scoring systems can be used in medical wards</p> <p>All scores perform better closer to clinical deterioration</p> <p>Limitations: Retrospective chart case-control study that involved chart reviews</p>

					Application to practice: NEWS is modeled on ViEWS, which had an AUC = 0.75 and detects clinical deterioration in medical patients
<p>A validation of NEWS to discriminate clinical deterioration, compared to 33 other EWSs</p> <p>Smith, Prytherch, Meredith, Schmidt, and Featherstone (2013)</p>	<p>Retrospective record review</p> <p>IV: NEWS tool components</p> <p>DV: death, CA, ICU admission</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 35, 585 patient episodes</p> <p>MAU in England</p> <p>May 2008 through June 2008</p>	<p>Mean and SD on all physiologic measures: RR, T, SpO², SBP, LOC</p> <p>AUROC was used to discriminate sensitivity of the NEWS to determine adverse outcomes, compared to 33 other EWSs (0.5 = minimum, 0.7 = reasonable, and 0.8 = good)</p>	<p>AUROC for NEWS values:</p> <p>Cardiac arrest, unanticipated ICU admission, death = 0.72</p> <p>Cardiac arrest in 24 h = 0.857</p> <p>ICU admission within 24 h = 0.857</p> <p>Death 24 h = 0.894</p>	<p>NEWS demonstrated good ability to discriminate patients at risk of combined outcome cardiac arrest, unanticipated ICU admission, or death within 24 h better than 33 other EWSs</p> <p>Thus, it can be a good predictor of clinical deterioration and timely interventions</p> <p>Application to practice: NEWS is the tool used in my QI and will be adapted to oncology septic patients who are clinically deteriorating.</p>
<p>Developed an evidence-based, patient-specific protocol for the management of</p>	<p>Retrospective observational study</p> <p>IV: use of a CCDS tool</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 163</p> <p>Tertiary care center in Texas</p>	<p>Patients with SIRS (score > 4)</p> <p>Infection identified in 64 of these patients.</p> <p>Sepsis confirmed in 45</p>	<p>The screening tool yielded a sensitivity of 96.5%, a specificity of 96.7%, a positive predictive value of</p>	<p>The three-step sepsis screening tool was a valid tool for the identification of sepsis</p>

<p>patients in a SICU and utilized a computerized clinical decision support tool</p> <p>Moore, Jones, Kreiner, McKinley, Sucher, Todd, . . . Moore (2009)</p>	<p>DV: source of infection, pna, soft tissue, urinary tract, abdominal surgery, drains, purulent drainage, temperature, blood, leukocyte count, oxygenation, chest x-ray</p>		<p>patients</p> <p>Phase 1 patients were identified with severe SIRS ≥ 4 and possible infection</p> <p>Phase 2 provides records of the SIRS data and possible infection</p> <p>In Phase 3, the intensivist identifies whether the patient meets the criteria for severe sepsis/septic shock, records a diagnosis, and, if criteria are met, initiates sepsis management protocol-directed team</p>	<p>80.2%, and a negative predictive value of 99.5%</p> <p>109 cases of sepsis among 93 patients 9/93 had multiple episodes of sepsis</p> <p>Of the 109 true cases, 56 were managed by the multidisciplinary SICU team</p> <p>The two sources of infection were abdominal 32% and blood stream 29%</p>	<p>The tool improved the screening but did not entirely account for all episodes of sepsis, in part due to lack of clinician knowledge to identify early sepsis. Need to automate the process.</p> <p>Application to practice: My project will involve testing a paper protocol tool that requires a score of 6 or $>$ for sepsis. This study lends support to an automated clinical tool</p>
<p>To better define mortality, LOS, cost, and risk factors associated with mortality and prolonged hospitalization in cancer patients with FN</p> <p>Kuderer, Dale, Crawford, Cosler, and</p>	<p>Longitudinal retrospective study</p> <p>IV: FN, cancer type</p> <p>DV: hospital LOS, inpatient mortality, total hospital cost</p>	<p>$N = 41,799$ from 115 US medical centers. Data were obtained from the University Health System Consortium (UHC) hospitalization database</p> <p>Patients were identified for inclusion by their ICD-9-CM</p>	<p>FN patients between 1995 and 2000</p> <p>The investigators looked at the discharge summaries</p> <p>The data were obtained from UHC longitudinal hospitalization database</p>	<p>In-hospital mortality was 9.5%. With no major comorbidities, 2.6% risk of mortality.</p> <p>One major comorbidity was associated with a 10.3% risk of mortality and more than one major comorbidity with a $\geq 21.4\%$ risk</p>	<p>The evidence suggests that early implementation of evidence-based, sepsis-specific therapies saves lives</p> <p>The early identification of sepsis remains challenging</p> <p>Identifying the signs</p>

Lyman (2006)		Code, range 140.00–208.9, to identify FN.	<p>Patients were categorized into three groups:</p> <p>Group 1: FN as a principal diagnosis</p> <p>Group 2: Patients with other principal diagnoses, and FN as secondary diagnosis</p> <p>Group 3: Patients with other principal diagnoses, and FN as a secondary diagnosis</p>	<p>of mortality, respectively</p> <p>Mean LOS was 11.5 (6) days, and the mean cost was \$19,110 per episode of FN.</p> <p>Independent major risk factors for inpatient mortality included invasive fungal infections, gram-negative sepsis, pna and other lung disease, and cerebrovascular, renal, and liver disease.</p> <p>Main predictors for LOS >10 days included leukemia, invasive fungal infections, other types of infections, and several comorbid conditions.</p>	<p>and symptoms of sepsis remains challenging</p> <p>The three-step sepsis screening tool was a valid tool for the identification of sepsis</p> <p>The tool improved the screening but did not entirely account for all episodes of sepsis, in part due to a lack of clinician knowledge to identify early sepsis</p> <p>Application to practice: Predictors of mortality in an FN population has application to practice and will enable me to control for those variables that are most associated with mortality</p> <p>With large data projects, there is a need to automate the process</p>
Clinical guidelines for the detection and management of sepsis in neutropenic patients	A panel of 13 experts in the field of infectious diseases, including experts in hematology and	A systematic literature search of Medline publications up to 2013	Risk factors for bacteremia: Neutropenia < 0.5 g/L, Antibiotics, Hickman catheter, chemotherapy	Each hour delay in broad-spectrum abx is associated with an average decrease of survival of 7.6%	Evidence supports B-lactam antibiotic +/- an aminoglycoside Normal saline was the

<p>Penack, Becker, Dieter, Maximilian, Kiehl, Von Lilienfeld-Toal, . . . Ostermann (2014)</p>	<p>oncology</p> <p>Key terms: sepsis, bacteremia, epidemiology, incidence, risk factors, prognosis, treatment, antibiotic, antifungal, cardiovascular, pulmonary failure, ventilation, renal dysfunction, renal failure, nutrition, growth factor, and transfusion</p>		<p>or surgery, acute myeloid leukemia</p> <p>Risk factors for severe sepsis: hypophosphatemia < 0.8, hypoproteinemia < 62 g/L</p> <p>Risk factors severe sepsis in FN: Procalcitonin > 1.5, lactate levels, decreased serum bicarb < 17 mmol/L, antithrombin < 70% or factor V11a < 0.8 ng/mL, and a low Multinational Association for Supportive Care in Cancer (MASCC) risk index score of <21</p>	<p>Meropenem is recommended</p> <p>Crystalloids to maintain cardiovascular function is crucial</p> <p>Positive pressure ventilation is preferred to prevent lung injury</p> <p>Renal replacement therapy for acute kidney injury in septic neutropenic patients</p> <p>Enteral feeds over parenteral is the preferred for nutritional consideration</p> <p>Insulin for control of hyperglycemia</p>	<p>preferred method to keep mean arterial blood pressure >65 mmHg</p> <p>For moderate to severe respiratory insufficiency, endotracheal intubation is recommended</p> <p>Acute kidney injury can be treated with renal replacement therapy.</p> <p>Application: These guidelines were used to guide my definitions of sepsis</p>
<p>Systematic review was to provide a summary of factors associated with reduced mortality in patients with neutropenic fever</p>	<p>Studies were identified that considered risks of infections: Multidrug resistant bacteria Improved quality of care Use of valid clinical</p>	<p>A systematic literature search of 88 US and international publications from 2008 up to 2015</p>	<p>Studies included the German Society of Hematology and Medical Oncology guidelines, recognition and management of sepsis in this patient group, standards of</p>	<p>Neutropenic fever in patients who were receiving cytotoxic chemotherapy varies with the underlying malignancy 5–10% in solid tumors to 100% in high-risk</p>	<p>Gram-negative bacteria confer the highest rate of mortality in FN patients</p> <p>Quality improvement programs must include an antibiotic</p>

<p>Thursky and Worth (2015)</p>	<p>assessment tools with neutropenic fever Use of the MASCC Score Early recognition of sepsis Reduction of time to antibiotic administration Role of biomarkers in monitoring neutropenic fever</p> <p>Key words: antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial stewardship, biomarkers, neutropenic fever, risk-assessment, and sepsis</p>		<p>care in high risk groups, and clinical pathways for sepsis</p>	<p>bone marrow transplant patients who are undergoing bone marrow transplantation</p> <p>Gram negative and antimicrobial-resistant pathogens are emerging as significant pathogens associated with neutropenic fever</p> <p>Valid tools for clinical assessment are required for management of neutropenic fever</p> <p>The MASCC score can identify patients who are suitable for discharge Quality improvement strategies include antimicrobial stewardship programs and clinical pathways for detection and management of sepsis</p> <p>Measurement of C-reactive protein and procalcitonin is beneficial at the patient level and holds</p>	<p>stewardship program</p> <p>Early detection of sepsis and use of valid tools for clinical assessment</p> <p>C-reactive protein and procalcitonin are beneficial for patient screening</p> <p>Overall, improve recognition of sepsis, facilitate administration of antimicrobial therapy and reduce mortality</p> <p>Application to practice: Early detection of sepsis and use of abx to target gram-negative organisms is key to decreasing mortality</p>
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				potential for future inclusion in clinical pathways	
<p>The application of goal-directed therapy in the treatment of severe sepsis and septic shock</p> <p>Rivers, Nguyen, Havstad, Ressler, Muzzin, and Knoblich (2001)</p>	<p>Experimental, randomized</p> <p>IV: early goal-directed therapy</p> <p>DV: mortality, lactate level, central venous saturation, time 7–72 hours, IV fluids, inotropic support</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 263</p> <p>9-bed ED at an 850-bed tertiary academic center</p> <p>March 1997 to March 2000</p>	<p>The patients were randomly assigned to the early goal-directed (EGD) group or standard (control) group.</p> <p>The EGD group received a central venous catheter for measurement of central venous oxygen saturation</p> <p>Each group received the following protocol: 500 ml bolus of crystalloid to keep central venous pressure 8 to 12 mm Hg</p> <p>A mean arterial pressure of 65 mm Hg and dobutamine to keep central venous oxygen saturation 70%</p>	<p>Mortality rates were significantly higher in the control group than in the EGD group ($p = 0.009$), as was mortality at 28 days ($p = 0.01$) and 60 days ($p = 0.03$)</p> <p>Both groups required the same amount of ventilation and inotropic support ($p < 0.001$), but the EGD group required more IV fluids</p>	<p>The benefits of EGD therapy in terms of outcome</p> <p>EGD resulted in less mortality due to CA</p> <p>The early identification of patients with illness allows for early implementation of goal-directed therapy. EGD provided at the earliest stages possible of severe sepsis and septic shock has significant short- and long-term benefits due to the recognition that these patients are at high risk for cardiovascular collapse</p> <p>Application: An EGD protocol can be applied to the management of septic patients, which will be done in my doctoral project</p>

<p>An American College of Chest Physicians/Society of Critical Care Medicine Consensus Conference was held in Chicago in 1991 with the goal of agreeing on a set of definitions that could be applied to patients with sepsis and its sequelae.</p> <p>Bone, Balk, Cerra, Dellinger, Fein, Knaus, and Sibbald (1992)</p>	<p>Consensus definition for sepsis.</p> <p>Key terms: infection, bacteremia, sepsis, septicemia, septic syndrome, and septic shock</p>	<p>Medical experts in the field convened to discuss a standardized definition</p>	<p>The standardization of terminology is necessary to eliminate confusion for researchers and clinicians.</p>	<p>The following recommendations were proposed:</p> <p>Sepsis implies a clinical response that arises from infection $T > 38\text{ C}$ or $< 36\text{ C}$ $HR > 90$ beats per minute $RR > 20$ breaths per minute $WBC > 12,000$ or $< 4,000$</p> <p>Severe sepsis is sepsis with organ dysfunction Septic-shock sepsis induces hypotension</p>	<p>Conventional terminology is considered inadequate to accurately characterized this syndrome</p> <p>The authors proposed a conceptual framework for organ system dysfunction and proposed a platform for future studies</p> <p>Application: Bone's consensus definition of sepsis is utilized my doctoral project</p>
<p>To assess the effects of mortality of compliance with a severe sepsis and septic shock management bundle as part of a QI bundle in 18 ICUs in 11 hospitals in Utah and Idaho.</p> <p>Miller, Dong, Nelson, Brown, Kuttler, Probst, and Clemmer (2013)</p>	<p>Quality improvement study</p> <p>IV: compliance with a severe sepsis and septic shock bundle</p> <p>DV: mortality, age, severity of illness, comorbidities</p> <p>Key terms: mortality, septicemia, outcome studies, QI</p>	<p>$N = 4,329$ patients with severe sepsis and septic shock</p> <p>18 ICUs in 11 hospitals in Utah and Idaho</p> <p>January 1, 2004 and December 31, 2010</p>	<p>Patients were classified into two groups: severe sepsis and septic shock</p> <p>The bundle elements were separated into 3-hour and 6-hour components</p>	<p>Mortality was 12% for the overall cohort, 17% for those with septic shock, and 8.9% for those with severe sepsis</p> <p>Concomitant 68% bundle compliance</p> <p>Mortality among subjects noncompliant with the total bundle decreased 55% over the study period, from</p>	<p>Compliance with early resuscitation elements completed within the first 3h after ED admission predicted greater ineligibility for inotropes, blood transfusions, ventilation, and glucocorticoids</p> <p>Identified four elements of the bundle associated with improved survival:</p>

				<p>21% at baseline to 9.7% in 2010</p> <p>Large absolute reduction to mortality 59% over 7 years, and bundle compliance went from 26% to 74% in 2010</p>	<p>inotropes, packed red blood cells, glucocorticoids, and mechanical ventilation</p> <p>Applications: The importance of treatment compliance, which is discussed as an outcome in my doctoral project</p>
<p>To determine whether clinical intervention by a medical emergency team prompted by clinical instability could reduce the incidence of mortality from unexpected CA in hospital.</p> <p>Buist, Moore, Bernard, Waxman, Anderson, and Nguyen (2002)</p>	<p>Non randomized quasi-experimental design</p> <p>IV: emergency response team</p> <p>DV: mortality, unexpected CA comorbidities</p> <p>Key terms: mortality, septicemia, outcome studies, QI</p>	<p>$N = 19,317$ in 1997 and $N = 22,847$ in 1999</p> <p>300-bed tertiary academic teaching center in Australia</p>	<p>Medical emergency team (two doctors and one senior intensive care nurse) attended clinically unstable patients immediately in a code-blue situation</p>	<p>The incidence of CA was 3.77 per 1,000 hospital admissions (73 cases) in 1996 pre-intervention and 2.05 per 1,000 admissions (47 cases) in 1999 post-intervention; mortality was 77% and 55%, respectively</p> <p>There was a 50% reduction in the incidence of unexpected CA (odds ratio 0.50, 95% CI (0.35–0.73))</p>	<p>Early intervention by a medical emergency team reduced the incidence of unexpected CA by about half</p> <p>Subsequent mortality was reduced from 77% to 55% after the system had been introduced</p> <p>Reduction in mortality by 2 patients per 1,000</p> <p>Application: Clinical response teams are a valuable asset and can reduce mortality</p>

<p>To determine whether the cloud-based CDSS could detect sepsis</p> <p>Amland and Hahn-Cover (2014)</p>	<p>Retrospective cohort quality-improvement study</p> <p>IV: CDSS</p> <p>DV: sepsis detection, microbiology cultures, serology, chemistry, lactic acid</p> <p>Key terms: early recognition and detection of sepsis, patient safety and prevention, CDSS, electronic health record (EHR)</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 6200 hospitalizations <i>N</i> = 817 screened positive for sepsis</p> <p>Level 1 trauma center, Level 2 trauma center, a women's and children's hospital and children, and two community hospitals in the United States</p>	<p>Sepsis CDSS has distinct activation definition for SIRS and severe SIRS if clinical criteria align, an alert is activated, and criteria are saved with time-stamp information</p> <p>When the sepsis CDSS is in live surveillance mode, notifications are delivered to providers for action</p> <p>Patients were categorized into three groups: Cohort A: First alert activated Cohort B: Provider-suspected infection when the first alert was activated Cohort C: No diagnostics</p>	<p>Activation rate of 10 patients per day who activate a first alert in a 500-bed hospital</p> <p>Cohort B comprised 417 (51%) patients already suspected of infection when the system was activated</p>	<p>Cloud-based-sepsis CDSS integrated with the EHR was an effective approach toward early recognition of sepsis</p> <p>The system was dependent on diagnostics by the clinician, and, thus, there were many false negatives due to missing data</p> <p>This was a first attempt at using this technology, and the researchers acknowledged the need to examine other relationships between SIRS, severe sepsis, and shock</p> <p>Application: Paper protocols are not the most accurate method to collect data versus a cloud-based application with real-time data.</p>
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<p>To implement PEWS with an associated multi-disciplinary action algorithm in a Pediatric Hematology/Oncology unit and evaluate staff responses</p> <p>Demmel, Williams, and Flesch (2014)</p>	<p>Quality improvement study</p> <p>IV: PEWS</p> <p>DV: CA, staff responses</p> <p>Key terms: pediatric deterioration, PEWS, failure to rescue</p>	<p>2007 pediatric patients in the Hematology/Oncology unit</p> <p>Medical Hematology/Oncology unit</p> <p>Children's Hospital Medical Center</p>	<p>PDSA cycle for change as part of the QI study</p>	<p>Three revisions were made since its inception in September 2007, based on reviewed data and feedback from all care team members</p> <p>Feedback from the staff regarding the PEWS was favorable</p> <p>29% response rate from the nursing staff, and 36% response rate from the residents.</p>	<p>The system removed barriers that prevented timely referral of children who are clinically deteriorating and require immediate help</p> <p>The days between CA events due to PEWS improved to threefold</p> <p>Less desirable input from the staff regarding the tool was that the scoring every 4 hours is rather mundane and monotonous for patients with lower PEWS scores</p> <p>Future enhancements would include blood pressure parameters</p> <p>Applications: The NEWS tool for my doctoral project has some similarities to PEWS, and this study provides a good framework for a QI project</p>
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<p>To determine the prevalence and impact on mortality of delays of effective antimicrobial therapy from initial onset of recurrent/persistent hypotension of septic shock</p> <p>Kumar, Roberts, Wood, Light, Parrillo, Sharma, . . . Cheang (2006)</p>	<p>Retrospective case-control study between July 1989 and June 2004</p> <p>IV: recurrent hypotension</p> <p>DV: survival to discharge, time to initiation, types of infection, antimicrobial use</p>	<p>$N = 2,731$</p> <p>Medical records of patients with septic shock</p>	<p>Three cohorts:</p> <p>First cohort: All septic shock admitted to ICU from medical and surgical wards Second cohort = Septic shock patients</p> <p>Third cohort: Patients whose information was obtained from ICD-9 codes</p>	<p>Strong correlation between delay in antibiotic administration and in-hospital mortality 95% CT 1.103–1.136, $p < .0001$</p>	<p>Effective antimicrobial administration within the first hour of documented hypotension was associated with increased survival rate</p> <p>Mortality rate is affected by antibiotic delays, and only 50% of septic shock patients received effective antimicrobial therapy within 6 hours</p> <p>Application: The importance of timely administration of abx in neutropenic patients, which is a variable that I will be measuring in my project</p>
<p>Inpatient sepsis statistics</p> <p>Hall, Williams, DeFrances, and Golosinskiy (2011)</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>Hospitalization rate:</p> <p>2000: 326,000/22.1 per 10,000</p> <p>2008: 727,000/37.7 per 10,000</p> <p>Under 65: 9.5 per 10,000</p> <p>Over 65: 122.2 per</p>	<p>Aging population with higher sepsis hospitalization</p> <p>Sepsis leads to longer hospital stay and more complications</p>

				<p>10,000</p> <p>Complication rate: Under 65: 2x longer Over 65: 26% more likely</p> <p>LOS: Overall: 75% longer Under 65: 2x longer Over 65: 43% longer</p> <p>Death and disposition: 17% of all inpatient death, half likely to discharge to home, 2x short-term acute, 3x long-term acute</p>	
<p>Guideline for sepsis treatment</p> <p>Dellinger, R. P., Levy, Rhodes, Annane, Gerlach, Opal, . . . Moreno (2013)</p>	<p>Consensus of the committee of 68 international experts who represented 30 international organizations</p> <p>Evidence-based recommendations on the assessment, development, and evaluation system to guide assessment of quality of evidence</p>	NA	NA	<p>Protocolized approach via EGD</p>	

<p>Compare the mortality of patients with (Group 2) and without (Group 1) implementation of sepsis bundles in the ED</p> <p>Wang, Xiong, Schorr, and Dellinger (2013)</p>	<p>Prospect study before and after design</p> <p>IV: SSC protocol and ICU admission</p> <p>DV: in-hospital sepsis mortality</p>	<p>N = 195 cases</p> <p>Group 1: 55/78 (70.8%) severe sepsis and 23/78 (29.5%) septic shock</p> <p>Group 2: 81/117 (69.2%) severe sepsis and 36/117 (30.8%) septic shock</p> <p>1,200-bed hospital in China with 15 ICU beds</p>	<p>Intervention-SSC guideline given to ED MD</p> <p>Poster protocol, daily patient screen, and compliance survey to identify failure to protocol compliance</p> <p>Standardized data collection with SSC</p>	<p>Low baseline SSC compliance: Rx dispensing, lack of prioritization, and MD unaware of abx timeline</p> <p>MD survey for noncompliance: 25.6% unsure, 16.4% forgot, 30.8% think no need, 5.8% did not know, 17.6% doctor or patient refusal</p> <p>Higher patient mortality in ED and not in ICU Increased LOS and mortality with > 6 hour delay in ICU transfer.</p>	<p>Decreased mortality after implementing sepsis protocol and QI in the ED</p> <p>Barriers: knowledge, attitude, and behaviors</p> <p>Application: Compliance is critical to reduce mortality, which will be assessed in my doctoral project</p>
<p>To describe the variations in incidence and mortality of severe sepsis in the United States using methods of data base extraction.</p> <p>Gaieski, Edwards, Kallan, and Carr (2013)</p>	<p>Retrospective cohort study</p> <p>IV: incidence and mortality of sepsis</p> <p>DV: ICD codes for sepsis, severe sepsis and septic shock, patient demographics, length of hospital stay, hospital-level characteristics</p>	<p>Used 4 nationally recognized studies</p> <p>ICD 9 codes for sepsis</p> <p>6-year period (2004-2009)</p> <p>Studies involved 44 US states</p>	<p>Used the National Inpatient data base Sample (NIS) from 2004 to 2009.</p> <p>Nationwide inpatient samples were stratified allowing for representative estimates of incidence and mortality</p> <p>Used 4 nationally</p>	<p>4-studies were analyzed. Incidences of sepsis across the 6-years per 100,000. Angus et al (8) Wang et al (12) Dombrovskiy et al (13) Martin et al (14)</p> <p>Regardless of method of data extraction: -there was a steady</p>	<p>There is an increased incidence of severe sepsis with a decrease in case fatality.</p> <p>One possible explanation is EGDT.</p> <p>The methods employed by Angus et al and Wang et al identify a group of patients which accurately</p>

			recognized studies	<p>increase in the annual incidence.</p> <p>-there was an annual decrease in case fatality and Dombrovskiy et al and Angus et al found a significant decrease</p> <p>Overall increase in sepsis 23.1%, severe sepsis 25.3%, and 18.2% septic shock.</p>	<p>reflect severe sepsis.</p> <p>Improved patient outcomes decreased and mortality has been proven by sepsis pathways, sepsis alerts and treatment bundles.</p> <p>The study emphasized the need to have a universal definition for sepsis so that sepsis can be accurately coded and treatment options defined.</p>
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Notes: AAU = acute admissions unit, abx = antibiotics, AIDS = acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, ALOC = altered level of consciousness, AP = arterial pressure, AUC = area under curve, AUROC = area under receiver operating characteristic curve, CA = cardiac arrest, CAU = clinical assessment unit, Chemo = chemotherapy, CI = confidence interval, DIC = disseminated intravascular coagulopathy, ED = emergency department, EWS = early warning system, FN = febrile neutropenia, HR = heart rate, ICS = intervention-calling score, ICU = intensive care unit, LOC = level of consciousness, LOS = length of stay, MAU = medical assessment unit, MEDS = mortality in emergency department sepsis, MEWS = modified early warning system, NEWS = national early warning system, O₂ sat = oxygen saturation, OLS = online survey, PDSA = plan-do-study-act, PEWS = pediatric early warning system, plt = platelet, pna = pneumonia, PSST = pre-hospital sepsis screening tool, QI = quality improvement, RC = regression coefficients, ROC = receiver operating characteristic, RR = respiratory rate, Rx = prescription, SBP = systolic blood pressure, SIRS = systemic inflammatory response syndrome, SOFA = sequential organ failure assessment score, SpO₂ = oxygen saturation level, SSC = surviving sepsis campaign, STD = survival to discharge, T = temperature, ViEWS = VitalPac early warning score system, VR = ventilatory frequency.